

The Darker the Riskier?: A Mixed-Methods Study Exploring Dark Triad Personality Traits as Predictors of Risky Sexual Behaviours

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ABSTRACT

Risky sexual behaviours, including unprotected sex, having multiple sexual partners, and sending explicit images, are popular amongst young adults, yet motivations underpinning engagement are underdeveloped. While research suggests dark triad personalities are a predictor of these behaviours, the findings are predominantly quantitative, lacking qualitative depth. A mixed-methods design (convergent parallel), situated within a social constructionist framework, combined quantitative surveys (risky sexual behaviours scale and SD-3) with open-ended questions, analysed using multiple linear regression and thematic analysis, within a group of Psychology students at a British university ($N = 122$). Results found psychopathy to be the only significant predictor of risky sexual behaviours. Thematic analysis revealed various themes, surrounding relationship dynamics, gratification, situational factors, and social influences. Findings suggest a difference in motivations between clinical and subclinical presentation of dark triad traits. Future research should explore the difference between irrational and strategic motives surrounding risky sexual behaviours, enhancing understanding and reducing stigma.

INTRODUCTION

Risky sexual behaviour (RSB) is increasingly being practiced among young people (Jepsen et al., 2023). These behaviours include sex for enjoyment, sex with different partners for sexual intercourse and sending sexual pictures (known as 'sexting'), which also reflects the evolving social norms surrounding sexuality, relationship structures, and digital communication (Bisson & Levine, 2009; Matsick et al., 2013). Although often consensual, these behaviours still carry considerable risk towards physical health, psychological well-being, and interpersonal relationships, which can impact an individual's physical health, emotional wellbeing, and ability to maintain healthy relationships. This includes exposure to sexually transmitted infections (STIs), emotional distress, and vulnerability to exploitative sexual relationships via non-consensual sharing of images (Jepsen et al., 2023), hence it is important to understand what drives individuals to engage in these behaviours to develop knowledge of how to effectively address sexually exploitative motivations towards others and improve the development of sexual health programmes.

In psychological research, RSB is a broad term for any sexual behaviour that increases the chances of negative physical, psychological, or social outcomes such as unwanted pregnancy, emotional disconnect from sexual partners and shame received from others due to personal sexual choice (Omuemu et al., 2020). In this study, RSB is operationalised as including three key behaviours: engaging in unprotected sex without using a condom; focusing on pleasure, engaging with multiple sexual partners (such as 'friends with benefits', non-monogamy and polyamorous relationships), and sending explicit sexual images (known as 'sexting'). These behaviours are becoming more common due to increased digital use allowing sexual interaction to be initiated remotely, increased social media use like dating platforms, and

shifting sexual norms like sex without romantic commitment (Barrense-Dias et al., 2017).

While these actions are often consensual and not intentionally harmful, they may still result in relational strain, emotional consequences, or vulnerability to exploitation, therefore it warrants a deeper investigation into the personality traits.

Based on literature, RSB has been connected through correlational studies involving maladaptive personality traits, specifically with the Dark Triad: psychopathy, narcissism and Machiavellianism (Paulhus & Williams, 2002). Despite being three distinct personalities, they share similarities in manipulateness, a lack of empathy, and social hostility.

psychopathy is characterised by emotional insensitivity, impulsivity, and emotional detachment (De Brito et al., 2021; Skeem et al., 2011) that can be argued to have sadistic intentions (Sofra, 2020) towards others in a similar nature to narcissism which is associated with constant need for admiration and inflated self-importance (Brown et al., 2009); whilst Machiavellianism involves strategic manipulation and emotional coldness (Shafti, 2023). These traits may contribute to boundary violations, emotional dysregulation, and impulsive decision-making in sexual contexts.

Further studies outlined by Zeigler-Hill et al. (2016) found a connection between Dark Triad personality factors and RSB, with the strongest predictor being psychopathy leading to sexual harassment behaviour due to impulsivity and a lack of empathy that reduces concern for others, increasing focus on personal gratification. Morelli et al. (2021) in a cross-national survey across 11 countries found psychopathy and narcissism as more predictive factors in 'sexting behaviours'. These traits were linked to emotional detachment and a focus on self-enhancement, which enabled engagement in sexting without emotional connection.

Similarly, Jones and Weiser (2014) found Machiavellianism to forecast infidelity, due to more manipulative and exploitative interpersonal styles that prioritise personal gain over trust or

loyalty, undermining healthy, consensual relationships. Findings collectively suggest Dark Triad traits as dispositional risk factors for RSB by influencing the manner in which individuals evaluate risk, relational boundaries, and sexual satisfaction.

However, these studies present several limitations, focusing only on coercive and hostile behaviour; manipulation, harassment, infidelity, and the complete extremes of antisociality. This is without attention towards behaviours such as unprotected sex for pleasure, multiple sexual partners for pleasure, and internet-related sexual sharing of images, that while not necessarily pathological, may be impacted by the same personality dynamics (Figueredo et al., 2015). The limited focus reduces exploration for normative sexual experiences which limits applicability to younger adults, who are statistically likely to engage in such behaviours (Jepsen et al., 2023). Furthermore, Balcioglu et al., (2023) explored psychopathy, Machiavellianism, and narcissism linking to sexual violence due to low empathy levels but only used male offenders which further makes it challenging to generalise.

Fortunately, studies highlighted emotional mechanisms that bridge personality traits and RSB. Madonna and Rangaiah (2023) found that insecure attachment styles predict engagement in consensual but unwanted sex; agreeing to sex despite not wanting to out of pressure or obligation, and Dark Triad traits acted as partial mediators in this relationship, suggesting personality traits not only influence engagement in behaviour but the rationale, emphasising the importance of understanding individuals' motivations and internalised beliefs about sexual behaviour. Despite scope of exploration, this relies on forensic or clinical samples, which lack applicability towards non-clinical groups such as younger adults.

Methodologically, studies are heavily reliant on quantitative self-report measures. Whilst these are standardised methods for measuring behaviour and correlational patterns, they can

overlook complex social and emotional factors that influence behaviour such as emotional drivers of dark traits and person-situation interaction that influence behaviour (Moor & Anderson, 2019). For instance, narcissism may statistically correlate with multiple sexual partners but lacks the exploration for underlying motivations; topics around peer pressure, emotional gratification, or feelings of empowerment, limiting the depth of insight into participants' psychological and social reasoning, leaving a gap in understanding individual perceptions of their sexual decisions.

Further complexities arise in digital contexts. Moor and Anderson (2019) found that Dark Triad personalities are likely to engage in unhealthy online behaviours, especially in anonymous environments that support impulsivity and emotional detachment. As 'sexting' and sexual expression online increase in normalisation, it is important to investigate Dark Triad traits and how they function in virtual environments in the form of sending sexually explicit images. Digital sexual behaviour may obscure traditional moral and relational boundaries, underscoring the need for research that accounts for both personality and environmental influences.

Drawing on a social-psychological framework, this study seeks to examine the extent to which psychopathy, narcissism, and Machiavellianism predict engagement in RSBs: unprotected sex, multiple sexual partners, and sending explicit sexual images. These behaviours were chosen because of increasing frequency, significance to public health, and established links to traits such as impulsivity, sensation-seeking, and resistance to social norms (Jepsen et al., 2023; Morelli et al., 2021; Babakr & Fatahi, 2023). Though non-coercive, these behaviours still involve significant risk and may reflect underlying personality dynamics.

This mixed methods approach has a number of advantages. First, it facilitates triangulation, where quantitative answers identify patterns of correlation between Dark Triad personality and risky sexual behaviour, while qualitative responses reveal the individual reasons behind these behaviours, both adding validity and richness (McLeod, 2024). Second, by integrating both strands, the research overcomes the primary methodological shortcomings of the existing literature, eschewing quantitative focused methods and embracing qualitative approaches to interpretation-sensitive explanations. Mixed methods are particularly valuable for studying complex psychological constructs since they allow researchers to explore both "what" happens and "why" it happens within the same study design (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2018). Third, the integration of open-ended qualitative responses with behavioural measures permit a more subtle exploration of how Dark Triad traits influence sexual decision-making in everyday life. Finally, by focusing on a non-clinical sample, this study enhances ecological validity and provides insights into public health and educational settings.

Accordingly, it is hypothesised that psychopathy, narcissism, and Machiavellianism will each be significant predictors of engagement in risky sexual behaviours. For further exploration, the study seeks to explore the underlying motivations for such behaviours through the following qualitative research questions: What influences individuals to engage in unprotected sex? What are the reasons for engaging in sexual activity with multiple sexual partners? What motivates the sharing of explicit sexual images? By examining both the statistical associations and the subjective reasoning behind these behaviours, this research aims to offer an empirically grounded psychological account of how Dark Triad traits influence sexual conduct in risky sexual behaviours (See Figure 1). Becoming applicable to public health policy, clinical intervention, and sex education programs by demonstrating dispositional tendencies in conjunction with situational characteristics for sexual risk-taking.

Figure 1.

Visual map of the study illustrating proposed relationship between Dark Triad personalities and risky sexual behaviour, incorporating qualitative and quantitative analyses

METHOD

Participants

Participants were 150 undergraduate psychology students at the University of Leicester, recruited through opportunity sampling via the EPR system in exchange for credit points. Only eligibility requirements were to be at least 18 years old and enrolled at the university. No exclusion criteria were applied based on gender, sexual orientation, or relationship status. Based on the sample demographic, it was deemed suitable for studying sexually active young adults at university (Chanakira et al., 2014). Participants were informed that their responses were anonymous alongside trigger warnings (See Appendix A).

Given the sensitive nature of the survey content, which included questions related to sexual behaviour and personality traits, demographic data such as age and gender were intentionally excluded, enhancing participant anonymity and comfort, in an attempt to reduce social desirability bias and increase the likelihood of honest responses. Research suggests that minimising identifiable information in studies addressing stigmatised topics can improve data quality while upholding ethical standards for confidentiality and participant wellbeing (Tourangeau & Yan, 2007). While this limits the ability to conduct demographic subgroup analyses, it supports the ethical integrity of the study design.

Out of the 150, 28 were excluded for failing an attention-check item within the SD-3, leaving a sample of 122 participants. Attention checks were used to ensure reliability of data within sensitive self-reported studies (Meade & Craig, 2012). A priori power analysis conducted using G*Power 3.1 (Faul et al., 2009) indicated a minimum sample of $N = 119$ necessary for medium effect size ($f^2 = 0.15$) with $\alpha = .05$ and power = .95, confirming adequate statistical power (See Appendix B).

For the qualitative portion, 44 individuals filled in open-ended questionnaires on unprotected sex, 14 filled in questionnaires on having multiple sexual partners, and 23 filled in questionnaires on explicit pictures. These further questions were conditionally responded on the basis of self-reported behaviour within the last six months of answering the survey. Ethical approval was granted by the University of Leicester (See Appendix C).

Design

The current research applied a mixed-methods, convergent parallel design, wherein both types of data were collected simultaneously, analysed independently and later integrated for interpretation (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011) (See Figure 2). This design was chosen to enable a detailed insight into both the statistical correlation between traits and behaviours, and the underlying individual motivations, enabling a more nuanced, rich exploration of RSB than would be achieved with a single-method approach.

All participants completed quantitative measures including a custom-developed Likert-scale RSB questionnaire and the Short Dark Triad (SD-3) personality scale (Jones & Paulhus, 2014). Those who provide high frequency scores for RSB were asked follow-up qualitative questions relating to their behaviours (See Figure 2). The predictor variables were Machiavellianism, narcissism, and psychopathy as measured by the SD-3, while the outcome variable is RSB; the frequency of unprotected sex, multiple sexual partners, and sending explicit sexual images combined as one.

Figure 2.

Visual map showcasing a convergent-parallel design, incorporating the SD-3 and RSB Questionnaire for quantitative analysis, and follow-up open-ended questions for qualitative analysis, with results being compared and integrated for interpretation

This correlational, non-experimental design was enabled by a multiple regression analysis to quantify the predictive strength of each personality dimension. Within-subjects design was employed, in the sense that all participants were presented with the same set of measures, making it possible to compare within persons and enhancing internal consistency and statistical power without requiring between-group comparisons. To reduce social desirability bias, all data were collected anonymously, and survey items were presented to all participants in the same way. Qualitative questions were only given to those participants reporting greater behavioural engagement to maintain relevance and in-depth responses, allowing for a

methodological triangulation approach to enhance the depth and validity of findings alongside survey data.

To provide a comprehensive description of Dark Triad personalities and risky sexual behaviours (RSB), results from the open-ended qualitative questions and quantitative survey findings will be integrated to cross-check and complement each other based on the patterns of the final results. This approach is consistent with the convergent parallel design, which emphasises the utilisation of multiple sources of data to enhance the interpretation and validity of findings.

Materials

The internet questionnaire, on JISC software, comprised three parts. Firstly, a purposefully developed 15-item RSB questionnaire for the current study contained five questions addressing unprotected sex, multiple sexual partners, and sending sexually explicit pictures. Responses were scored on a Likert scale (Never, Rarely, Sometimes, Often and Always), and high ratings indicated higher engagement. All questions are describing behaviour during the previous 6 month period of survey completion (See Appendix D).

Open-ended questions targeting individuals who reported "Sometimes," "Often," or "Always" in responding to any of the RSB behaviours. These were inquiries as to why, what thinking took place, and behavioural contexts. At least a 10-word response was required to initiate depth (See Appendix E).

This was followed by a Short Dark Triad (SD-3) scale (Jones & Paulhus, 2014), 27 items, nine for each of Machiavellianism, narcissism, and psychopathy, which were rated using a Likert scale (Strongly Disagree, Disagree, Neutral, Agree and Strongly Agree). Higher ratings reflected higher endorsement of the specific trait (See Appendix F).

Procedure

Participants were referred to the JISC survey web page, where they read an information sheet (See Appendix G) followed by GDPR Privacy Notice (See Appendix H). Once read, participants were asked to provide electronically informed consent (See Appendix I).

Participants were informed that their participation was voluntary, their responses would be anonymous, and they could withdraw at any time prior to submission. A content warning was also provided due to the sensitive nature of the study.

Following consent, participants completed the 15-item RSB questionnaire. Participants who reported moderate to high levels of each behaviour were then presented with a series of open-ended questions relating to that behaviour. All participants then completed the 27-item SD-3 scale. Participants then saw a debrief page (See Appendix J) which repeated the study's purpose and provided links for NHS sexual health information, free STI testing, and mental health support sites. As data collection was anonymous, it was not feasible for participants to withdraw after submission, this was informed in the consent form page of the survey (See Appendix I). The entire questionnaire took approximately 5 minutes, with individuals who were completing qualitative items tendentially taking longer.

Data Analyses

All quantitative data were analysed using JASP (version 0.19.3). Scale scores were treated as interval-level data and subjected to parametric analysis. Negatively worded SD-3 items were reverse-scored prior to subscale sums being totaled. Reliability was assessed via Cronbach's alpha, with results indicating excellent internal consistency for the unprotected sex subscale ($\alpha = .94$) and good consistency for both multiple sexual partners ($\alpha = .84$) and explicit sexual images ($\alpha = .81$). The SD-3 subscales exhibited acceptable reliability: Machiavellianism ($\alpha = .74$), narcissism ($\alpha = .76$), and psychopathy ($\alpha = .76$) (See Appendix K).

Multiple linear regressions were conducted to determine the unique predictive value of each personality trait, accounting for shared variance across traits using two-tailed significance levels ($\alpha = .05$) for all inferential tests (See Appendix L). Pearson's correlation coefficients were calculated to assess bivariate correlations among personality traits and each RSB type (See Appendix M). Regression assumptions were examined and met: linearity, residual normality (via Q-Q plots), multicollinearity (tolerance and VIF), and autocorrelation (Durbin-Watson statistics) were all within acceptable limits (See Appendices N to Q).

Regression diagnostics identified outliers in models predicting multiple partners and explicit image behaviours. These were retained as they had minimal effect on the regression coefficients or levels of significance. The same results were obtained in sensitivity analysis with data points removed, attesting to stability and reliability of results (See Appendix R).

Qualitative Analysis

Open-ended responses were analysed using inductive thematic analysis (See Appendices S to AA). Only participants with high to moderate frequency of behaviours were considered for the salience of data. The responses were iteratively and manually coded to allow themes to emerge naturally. The codes were then organised into subthemes based on semantic similarity, and repeated steps for subthemes grouped into final themes. Analysis was driven by psychological theory, namely decision making and personality theory.

RESULTS

Quantitative Analysis:

Descriptive Statistics and Assumption Checks

Descriptive statistics were carried out for both Risky Sexual Behaviours (RSB) and individual behaviours as well as for psychopathy, narcissism and Machiavellianism based on all participants' responses ($N = 122$) (See Table 1)

Table 1.

Descriptive Statistics for Main Study Variables

	<i>N</i>	Minimum	Maximum	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>
RSB Summary Score	122	15	49	23.37	9.04
Machiavellianism Summary Score	122	15	41	27.39	5.58
Narcissism Summary Score	122	11	38	25.09	5.77
Psychopathy Summary Score	122	9	35	18.74	5.30
Unprotected Sex Summary Score	122	5	25	9.77	6.28
Multiple Sexual Partners Summary Score	122	5	18	6.30	2.78
Sending Explicit Images Summary Score	122	5	25	7.26	3.25

Note. N = sample size. M = mean score. SD = standard deviation.

RSB mean score was 23.37 ($SD = 9.04$) ranging from 15 (lowest possible score) to 49 (75 was the maximum possible score). Analysing the behaviours individually, unprotected sex (US) had a mean score of 9.77 ($SD = 6.28$), with multiple sexual partners (MSP) mean score of 6.29 ($SD = 2.78$), and sending explicit sexual images (ESI) mean score of 7.26 ($SD =$

3.22). All behaviours had a minimum score of 5 (lowest possible score), with maximum scores ranging from 18 (MSP) to 25 (US and ESI) with 25 being the maximum possible score.

Exploring individual traits, participants scored higher in Machiavellianism ($M = 27.39$, $SD = 5.58$), followed by narcissism ($M = 25.09$, $SD = 5.77$), and psychopathy ($M = 18.74$, $SD = 5.30$). Psychopathy has a minimum score of 9 (lowest possible score) and maximum of 35, followed by narcissism having a minimum score of 11 and maximum of 38, then Machiavellianism having a minimum score of 15 and maximum of 41 (45 being the maximum possible score).

Visual analysis of histograms revealed a positive skewness within all three of RSBs (See Appendix AB), suggesting very low to moderate levels of engagement in these behaviours and fewer reports of higher engagement. On the contrary, Dark Triad traits all presented with bell-shaped curves (See Appendix AC), suggesting an approximate normal distribution, therefore can justify the use of the multiple linear regression model without any transformations.

Assumption checks were conducted to assess the regression results for the overall RSB. Assumptions of linearity were explored using residuals vs. predicted value plots which showed no distinct curvilinear patterns, proposing a general linear relationship. However, a diagonal cluster within the negative residuals was observed, though being a concern, there was a positively skewed distribution in the dependent variable which can impact the residuals. As highlighted by Pallant (2020), this pattern is common in behavioural data and does not invalidate the analysis providing the rest of the assumptions are met. With that in mind, Q-Q plots proved a residual pattern following an expected diagonal with no influential

cases, which supports the normality of residuals. All standardised residuals were within ± 3.29 suggesting no extreme outliers (Field, 2016). Homoscedasticity was confirmed via visual inspection of the residual plots, showing a fairly even spread. Independence of errors was supported by the Durbin-Watson statistic of 1.76, falling under the acceptable range.

Multicollinearity was not a concern, as all Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) values ranged from 1.06 to 1.35 and condition indices are below the threshold value of 15 which sparks no concern. Overall, these diagnostics confirm that the assumptions within multiple linear regression were met (See Appendices N to Q).

Overall Risky Sexual Behaviours (RSB)

Upon assessing the multiple linear regression, the model showed that the Dark Triad traits had in fact predicted risky sexual behaviours (See Table 2).

Table 2.

Model summary for Predicting Risky Sexual Behaviours (RSB)

Model	R	R^2	Adjusted R^2	RMSE	Durbin-Watson
M ₁	.41	.17	.15	8.36	1.76

Note. M₁ includes psychopathy, narcissism, and Machiavellianism scores.

The model was statistically significant, $F(3, 118) = 7.83, p < .001$, accounting for 16.6% of the variance in RSB scores (Adjusted $R^2 = .15$), Cohen's $f^2 = .20$, indicating a medium effect size (Cohen, 1988) that suggests the predictors had a moderate impact on RSB (See Table 3).

Table 3.

ANOVA Summary for RSB Regression

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p
Regression	1641.87	3	547.29	7.83	< .001
Residual	8246.53	118	69.89		
Total	9888.40	121			

Upon looking at the traits individually (See Table 4), only psychopathy had significantly predicted RSB ($\beta = .35, p < .001$), while narcissism ($\beta = .14, p = .10$) and Machiavellianism ($\beta = .03, p = .78$) were not significant (See Figure 3).

Table 4.

Coefficients for Predicting Risky Sexual Behaviours (RSB)

Predictor	<i>B</i>	<i>SE</i>	β	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	95% CI (Lower)	95% CI (Upper)
Intercept	5.40	4.65		1.16	.25	-3.81	14.61
Psychopathy	0.59	0.16	.35	3.62	< .001	0.27	0.92
Narcissism	0.23	0.14	.14	1.66	.10	-0.04	0.49
Machiavellianism	0.05	0.16	.03	0.28	.78	-0.27	0.36

Figure 3.

Path diagram of standardised regression coefficient for the prediction of overall RSB from Dark Triad personality traits

Unprotected Sex (US)

Exploring the behaviours individually, the regression model was significant for unprotected sex, $F(3, 118) = 4.10, p = .008$, explaining 9.4% of the variance (Adjusted $R^2 = .07$), Cohen's $f^2 = .10$, suggesting medium effect size, hence the predictors had a moderate impact on unprotected sex. Again, psychopathy was the only significant predictor ($\beta = .25, p = .01$) whilst narcissism ($\beta = .16, p = .09$) and Machiavellianism ($\beta = -.02, p = .89$) was not significant (See Figure 4). No potential outlier cases were identified.

Figure 4.

Path diagram of standardised regression coefficient for the prediction of unprotected sex from Dark Triad personality traits

Multiple Sexual Partners (MSP)

The regression model for multiple sexual partners was also significant, $F(3, 118) = 5.03, p = .003$, accounting for 11.3% of the variance (Adjusted $R^2 = .09$), Cohen's $f^2 = .13$ suggesting medium effect size, hence the predictors had a moderate impact on multiple sexual partners. Psychopathy significantly predicted multiple sexual partners ($\beta = .31, p = .002$), while narcissism ($\beta = .03, p = .70$) and Machiavellianism ($\beta = .038, p = .71$) were not significant (See Figure 5). Three cases were identified as potential outliers (Std. Residuals $> \pm 3$), but their Cook's Distance values were below 0.12, suggesting minimal influence on the model and therefore no change was made (See Appendix R).

Figure 5.

Path diagram of standardised regression coefficient for the prediction of multiple sexual partners from Dark Triad personality traits

Sending Explicit Sexual Images (ESI)

Lastly, sending sexual images was statistically significant too within the model, $F(3, 118) = 3.60, p = .016$, accounting for 8.4% of the variance (Adjusted $R^2 = .06$), Cohen's $f^2 = .09$ indicating a small effect size, suggesting a modest predictive impact on unprotected sex.

Psychopathy was a significant predictor ($\beta = .21, p = .04$). Both narcissism ($\beta = .07, p = .42$) and Machiavellianism ($\beta = .09, p = .36$) were not significant (See Figure 6). Three cases had standardised residuals exceeding ± 3 ; however, Cook's Distance values were below 0.36, indicating no major distortion of the model hence no changes made (See Appendix R).

Figure 6.

Path diagram of standardised regression coefficient for the prediction of sending sexually explicit images from Dark Triad personality traits

Correlational analysis of Dark Triad personalities and RSB

Pearson's correlation analysis was conducted in order to examine the bivariate correlations between each of the Dark Triad traits and risky sexual behaviours, including unprotected sex, multiple sexual partners, and explicit sexual image sharing (See Appendix M). Psychopathy was positively related to all three behaviours: unprotected sex ($r = .27, p = .003$), multiple sexual partners ($r = .32, p < .001$), and explicit image sharing ($r = .26, p = .003$). It also showed a significant correlation with overall RSB scores ($r = .38, p < .001$), indicating a strong and stable relationship. Machiavellianism was moderately correlated with explicit image sharing ($r = .21, p = .019$) and minimally with having multiple sexual partners ($r = .19, p = .04$), but not with unprotected sex ($r = .15, p = .11$); overall, it was modestly correlated with RSB ($r = .23, p = .011$). Narcissism was significantly but weakly related to unprotected sex ($r = .19, p = .041$) but was not significantly related to having multiple partners ($r = .076, p = .41$) or sharing explicit images ($r = .12, p = .18$). Overall, narcissism was weakly related to overall RSB ($r = .20, p = .03$). These results demonstrate that among the three traits, psychopathy is the most strongly and consistently associated with risky sexual behaviour across all domains.

Assumption Checks for RSB

All three models for the three RSB individually met assumptions for linearity despite the diagonal cluster in the negative residual which was established to be of no concern due to positive skew (See Appendix AB), independence of errors was met (Durbin-Watson values ≈ 2), and multicollinearity was not present as VIFs < 1.4 and Condition Indices < 15 . Residual plots and standardised residuals supported the assumption of normality (See Appendices N to Q).

Qualitative Analysis:

Unprotected Sex

Theme 1: Trust and Relationship Dynamics:

Participants stated that a trusting, monogamous relationship is a key influential factor that drives both parties to engage in unprotected sex, resulting in emotional bonding that creates a perception of safety: *“I have a partner who I trust and believe it is safe with them”* (Participant 20). For some, the decision was based on improving sexual pleasure for both parties, seeing protection as a barrier to maximise pleasure: *“it was for pleasure choices for both partners and convenience”* (Participant 44). Suggesting rational trust and personal preference contribute to an individuals’ willingness to engage in unprotected sex.

Theme 2: Risk-perception and Decision-Making:

Participants demonstrated their perception of low risk, such as the likelihood of catching STIs and unwanted pregnancy, that influenced their choice to engage in unprotected sex: *“I look at my likelihood of getting pregnant and catching a sexual disease, and if it’s unlikely/practically 0% chance then I won’t use protection.”* (Participant 92). Alternatively, participants suggested long-lasting alternatives to barrier methods as part of their risk-management strategies: *“I plan to get some non hormonal contraception like IUD”* (Participant 16). These findings highlighted diverse approaches to sexual decision-making such as risk assessment and alternative methods of protection, both influencing engagement in unprotected sex.

Theme 3: Psychological and Behavioural Factors:

Some participants stated engaging in unprotected sex as a consequence of impaired

judgement in the moment, especially when the decisions are being made during sex: *“I know its more beneficial to both me and him to use protection, but sometimes i forget about the pros and cons and we just get carried away in the moment.”* (Participant 24). Some participants stated no negative experiences of unprotected sex, therefore reinforcing the behaviour: *“I haven't experienced any issues yet. And worst case scenarios can always be resolved”* (Participant 70). These findings emphasise that unprotected sex is influenced by impulsive “heat of the moment” decision-making and lack of negative consequences from past experiences with unprotected sex.

Theme 4: Situational and External Influences:

Data from participants showed that their engagement in unprotected sex is influenced by the desire to improve sexual activity for others, even at the expense of personal comfort: *“boys say they enjoy it more (without a condom)”* (Participant 54). On the other hand, data highlighted the rising cost of condoms made them financially inaccessible, therefore not buying one is more convenient: *“It is more convenient (the price of condoms is insane)”* (Participant 115). Hence, findings suggest external factors such as meeting their partners sexual expectations and financial barriers to accessing condoms can shape decisions relating to unprotected sex.

Multiple Sexual Partners

Theme 1: Pleasure and Self-Gratification:

Participants expressed engaging in sexual activity with multiple sexual partners as an enjoyable and thrilling experience, particularly when meeting new people: *“I would prefer seeing previous partners too, I think it's enjoyable to experience new partners too”* (Participant 94). Additionally, some participants highlighted experiencing emotional

connection and psychological comfort from sexual partners, which enhanced intimacy: “*i think more an emotional connection i prefer*” (Participant 54). Such findings emphasise the need for emotional comfort and sexual novelty in contributing to fulfilling personal desires, allowing self-gratification and sexual stimulation to be achieved from multiple sexual partners.

Theme 2: Relationship Attitudes and Avoidance of Commitment:

Data from participants highlighted that exploring multiple sexual partners allows a person to discover themselves and their sexual preferences before settling for a romantic relationship: “*to be able to find your preferences you need to explore first before setting your heart down into one person for the rest of your life*” (Participant 34). This exploration was also associated with achieving personal sexual satisfaction: “*The ability to find someone that makes me feel sexually fulfilled*” (Participant 115). Conversely, some participants expressed disinterest in relationships because they are reluctant to commit to a single person: “*Not committed enough to one person*” (Participant 70). Overall, the findings suggest that for some, multiple sexual partnerships allows for sexual self-discovery and preparation for future commitment, while others choose to avoid commitment to increase sexual flexibility and personal fulfilment.

Theme 3: Personal and Lifestyle Factors:

Participants described their engagement with multiple sexual partners as a personal choice that contributed to their well-being and personal satisfaction: “*i do not think it is of much importance how many people i sleep with as long as it feels right to me.*” (Participant 35). Alongside personal needs, some participants framed this behaviour with multiple sexual partners as part of their personal routine that supported emotional stability: “*I get unhappy/*

low mood when my routine is not met.” (Participant 87). The findings propose that for some individuals, multiple sexual partners are part of their personal lifestyle by achieving personal sexual satisfaction, maintaining emotional balance and promoting overall well-being.

Theme 4: Social and Cultural Influence:

Some participants stated that social media has played a role in normalising low commitment relationships, encouraging engagement with multiple sexual partners: *“like social media has encouraged the low commitment situation concept”* (Participant 84). Others expressed a desire to challenge gender norms traditionally associated with men: *“It’s one of those scenarios where if a man can do it so should I”* (Participant 94). These findings highlight potential peer and cultural influences such as social media as well as evolving gender expectations. Hence, engaging with multiple sexual partners is not just a personal choice, but a response to social reinforcement and a form of gender empowerment.

Sending Explicit Sexual Images

Theme 1: Relationship and Emotional Motivations:

Participants in long-distance relationships described maintaining intimacy and sexual fulfillment through sending explicit images, with some noting that it enhanced their romantic bond: *“I think it’s quite important, and quite romantic too, for us to connect sexually without having to be with each other physically”* (Participant 60). In addition, trust is a key factor in the decision to send explicit images, contributing to an emotional connection: *“Personally I need somewhat of an emotional connection but the main aspect is about trust”* (Participant 69). Such findings highlight the importance of maintaining long-distance relationships through emotional intimacy and trust with the exchange of sexual images, facilitating sexual closeness and reinforcing romantic connection.

Theme 2: Sexual and Psychological Gratification:

Sending explicit images was described by participants as a way to stimulate sexual excitement and mutual satisfaction: “*enjoy the exciting feeling of sending explicit photos to my partner and receiving them*” (Participant 59). Beyond physical stimulation, some participants noted an improvement in self-esteem from receiving positive feedback when sending sexual images: “*It makes you feel good about yourself especially when you get compliments*” (Participant 64). Hence, the findings propose that sharing sexually explicit images fulfils both sexual and psychological needs, especially from emotional validation from a partner's response, enhancing self-worth and feelings of intimacy.

Theme 3: Situational and Ethical Considerations:

Some participants emphasised that they would only send sexually explicit images in specific circumstances, such as building rapport through a prolonged conversation: “*after you have had multiple conversations and are comfortable when the conversation leads to that*” (Participant 34). In addition, some participants acknowledged ethical concerns such as only sending images if the other person expresses mutual interest: “*it depends if other [person] want to continue to share in sending these types of images*” (Participant 73). These findings highlight the importance of contextual boundaries and consent for those engaging in sending explicit images, demonstrating their choices to engage in image sharing only when mutual interest, trust, and comfort were established.

Theme 4: External and Social Pressures:

Participants expressed their engagement with sharing sexually explicit images out of concern for disappointing their partners: “*when they ask for it and i don't want to disappoint or seem boring*” (Participant 30). In some cases, both partners were described as mutually reinforcing the behaviour: “*because we encourage each other to*” (Participant 69). These findings

suggest social and interpersonal pressures, including worry of disapproval and reciprocal partner influence, contribute to decisions surrounding sharing explicit images. For some individuals, the desire to maintain relational harmony or meet sexual expectations may override personal hesitation.

DISCUSSION

Comprehensive Understanding and Research Comparison

The present study aimed to investigate Dark Triad personality traits which include psychopathy, narcissism, and Machiavellianism as predictors of engagement in risky sexual behaviour (RSB), specifically unprotected sex, multiple sexual partners and sending explicit sexual images. Additionally, it also explores why participants are influenced and motivated to engage in the three risky sexual influences respectively, with results ranging from various areas of gratification, relationship dynamics and commitments, situational and personal circumstances, and societal impacts.

One of the key findings of this study was that psychopathy was a significant predictor of risky sexual behaviours (RSBs) and was the only Dark Triad trait to be positively correlated with all three types of RSBs. This can be explained by the archetypal traits of psychopathy for thrill-seeking, impulsivity, and absence of emotional attachment, which were also reflected in the thematic analysis, wherein participants accounted for increasing sexual stimulation and maintaining individual lifestyle satisfaction through engagement with multiple sexual partners. These findings are consistent with previous research: Skeem et al. (2011) and Jones and Weiser (2014) depicted psychopathy as being characterised by a lack of concern for others and sexual gratification at any expense. De Brito et al. (2021) also mentioned reinforcement-based decision-making in psychopathy, as behaviours leading to immediate gratification are most likely to be repeated. This was expressed in the participants' reports of constantly seeking out new sexual partners and sex as a means of attaining emotional stability through sexual gratification. These results must, however, be read in light of caution. Participants who scored higher on psychopathy and RSB come from a British

university and are not clinical diagnoses of psychopaths, and the large majority of participants reported using protective behaviours, for instance, negotiating alternative contraceptive use or relational trust before sending explicit images through prolonged conversations to build rapport. These accounts are distinct from typical psychopathic patterns of impulsivity and disregard for others. Thus, while some of the incentives for RSB; self-gratification, lacking relationship commitment, are parallel to psychopathic behaviour which can be interpreted as risk-taking (Babakr & Fatahi, 2023), the root incentives may be very different from a clinical psychopath to a young person with “psychopathic” tendencies (See Figure 7).

Figure 7.

Conceptual map illustrating how distinct positive and negative intentions may underlie risky sexual behaviour among individuals scoring high in psychopathic traits

For other participants, engagement in risky sexual activity might stem from situational factors, such as spontaneity in the "heat of the moment," and not because the person does not care about risk, but simply the person did not think about the risks in the first place. Given

that the sample included young adults with potential Dark Triad tendencies rather than clinical samples, future research should be careful to make particular distinctions between personality factors and situational factors in decision-making about risky sexual behaviours.

In addition to primary findings, Machiavellianism was found to have had a non-significant regression with RSB but a weak correlation with overall RSB. This suggests that while Machiavellianism does not necessarily predict risky sexual actions, there could be aspects of the personality that are associated with engagement in these behaviours. This finding partially contradicts the literature; Figueredo et al. (2015) discovered Machiavellianism was not strongly inclined towards sexual relationships, based on a preference for long-term strategy and not becoming involved in short-term commitment. In the present study, however, Machiavellianism was weakly correlated with having multiple sexual partners, possibly based on strategic behaviour consistent with Paulhus and Williams (2002), who described Machiavellianists as reality-based and goal-directed. This study supported the findings as certain participants described their use of multiple sexual partners to help them find a suitable romantic long-term partner, suggesting a more strategic approach to relationship formation, instead of engaging with several sexual encounters for sexual desire. Similarly, the absence of a significant correlation between Machiavellianism and unsafe sex is in line with Shafti (2023), who highlighted the pessimistic attitude of Machiavellianists, including assumptions that others are unsafe or untrustworthy sexual partners. In this regard, engaging in some RSBs, such as having multiple partners or sending explicit sexual images, can be better explained as strategic moves rather than impulsive risks (See Figure 8). It remains important to distinguish between Machiavellian tendencies and clinical Machiavellianism; whereas clinical Machiavellianists are defined by cold manipulation and emotional detachment

(Shafti, 2023), in the current research, most participants only discussed sending explicit images where mutual consent and emotional connection were present. This moral consideration suggests that while strategic elements of Machiavellianism may influence RSB, emotional involvement and reciprocity still moderate the behaviour of non-clinical samples like this study using a sample of young adults, which explains why the correlation is weak yet positive.

Figure 8.

Conceptual map illustrating how distinct positive and negative intentions may underlie risky sexual behaviour among individuals scoring high in machiavellian traits

Thus, future research may consider exploring the hidden agendas of RSB in Machiavellian young adults to determine whether it is due to exploitative intentions or strategic exploration.

In addition to that, this research demonstrated that narcissism had the weakest association with RSB among all Dark Triad traits, having a non-significant predictive regression and discovering weak correlations with unprotected sex and RSB. This was deemed surprising as it was different to what previous research has found; Babakr and Fatahi (2023) demonstrated that narcissism predicts dangerous behaviour, while Morelli et al. (2021) showed that there was a positive relationship between aggravated sexting and narcissism. One possible account of the current findings is that narcissists, because they need to maintain a high social image of themselves, may avoid high-risk behaviours that can damage their reputation. As such, it may explain the non-significant regression with RSB. This is further supported by Brown et al. (2009), who argued that narcissistic grandiosity may damage their social standing, therefore avoiding behaviours that can result in further destruction to their character such as participating with multiple sexual partners who may view the person as sexually unfit or sending explicit images that can be used against them. Thematic analysis suggested this indirectly as unprotected sex was mentioned to create a feeling of safety between partners, unlike in multiple sexual partners and sending explicit images where this idea was not mentioned, hence the weak correlation with unprotected sex where a level of safety seems guaranteed.

Similarly, Paulhus and Williams (2002) described narcissists as interpersonal irritants, and from this, proposed that individuals with high narcissistic traits might be especially sensitive to social rejection. Therefore, they would avoid RSB that would also jeopardise new interpersonal relationships or damage their public image. Though narcissism did not predict RSB as a whole, the weak positive correlations with total RSB can capture a central tendency

that is typical of narcissistic personality characteristics. It could be plausible that in some circumstances, the act of unprotected sex can be pursued based on selfish interest whereby perceived personal gain surpasses the other person's needs. For example, women are likely to experience greater reproductive and psychological risks from unsafe sex than men, whose primary risk may be sexually transmitted infections, which are typically treatable by modern medicine. Although the thematic analysis did not directly support this interpretation, it implies a likely explanation for why the weak associations were observed. Subsequent research must explore potential gender differences between young adults who score high on narcissistic traits to determine whether self-interest is manifested differently across risky sexual behaviours.

Regarding motivations behind unprotected sexual practices for pleasure, thematic analysis revealed that unprotected sex was significantly associated with trust, sense of risk control, and with obtaining mutual sexual gratification. Unprotected sex was significantly highlighted to help two individuals be more intimate and gratified, not solely for individual, personal enjoyment. The focus on relationship dynamics and unprotected sex highlights the desire to increase emotional and sexual closeness within the relationship by both parties. Interestingly enough, some of the participants did make the distinction that their primary incentive was maximising their partner's sexual satisfaction, even at the cost of their own safety needs. This finding presents a more differentiated picture than previous literature, which overall uses negative language to describe unprotected sex. For example, Jepsen et al. (2023) called the use of inadequate contraceptives "shame-ridden" and linked it with regret and negative decision-making. In contrast, however, the present research highlights that unprotected sex, in some relationship settings, can be considered a positive, intimacy-facilitating behaviour, especially since participants in this study demonstrated cautious risk-perception and offered

alternatives such as other forms of contraception such as IUD. Future studies need to continue to examine the role of shared sexual pleasure in condom-use decision-making and how widespread reasons for enhancing a partner's pleasure can be integrated into sexual health interventions, striking a balance between emotional intimacy and safer sex.

Another noteworthy finding was the consistency between the present study's findings and previous literature exploring motivations for engaging in multiple sexual partners. Bisson and Levine (2009) discovered a theme of low commitment in "friends with benefits" relationships, which is also consistent with the present thematic analysis, where participants described resistance to committing to a single partner and the use of multiple sexual partners to meet sexual desire without long-term relational commitment. Similarly, Matsick et al. (2013) found that multiple sexual partnerships support in the facilitation of emotional intimacy, which aligns with the manner in which participants explained seeking brief emotional connections in order to meet personal needs for emotional gratification. Adding onto the current research, the present study has found that multiple sexual partners are part of some participants' personal lifestyle, facilitating emotional wellbeing and self-rated sexual satisfaction. Yet it is important to note that the emotional impact of such arrangements is likely to be uneven between individuals and relationships, which was not explored within current literature. Future research must explore closely the emotional consequences of having multiple sexual partners, both beneficial as well as possibly detrimental consequences, to further our understanding of the complex relationship between emotional support and relational structures in contemporary sexual life.

Further exploring the motivations in contemporary sexual activity, the present study found excitement, stimulation, and social pressure as primary motivators for sending sexually explicit images. These findings are consistent with previous studies; Barrense-Dias et al.

(2017) found experience-seeking personality and peer pressure were associated with sexting behaviours. As suggested from the thematic analysis of this current study, individuals who are looking for sexual stimulation or are vulnerable to social influence may be more inclined to engage in the sharing of explicit images. The significant highlight of the use of explicit sexual images is how some individuals use the method to enhance their self-esteem and obtain positive comments from others receiving the images. Participants described sharing pictures not only for sexual gratification but also in order to receive positive feedback affirming their self-esteem. This finding contributes to the evolving body of knowledge of sexual image sharing practices by analysing emotional sexual motives to achieve emotional needs. Future studies should continue to explore the contribution of sending explicit images supporting a person's self-esteem, that is, whether self-esteem impacts are transient or persistent, and examine safer, alternative ways of satisfying individuals' need for self-validation while meeting sexual desires.

Implications and Clarifications

The present findings have several important implications for theory development and the clarification of existing frameworks. Firstly, the observation that the Dark Triad traits have differential relations with risky sexual behaviours suggests that future theories must move beyond broad generalisation of personality and risk-taking. Rather than assuming equivalent risk-enhancing effects, future models need to consider how traits such as psychopathy, Machiavellianism, and narcissism interact with situational, emotional, and relational processes in influencing sexual decision-making. The findings also shed light on existing theories by showing that certain risky sexual acts can take place not only as a result of

impulsivity or disregard for others, but for strategic, emotional, or reputational reasons, especially in non-clinical young adult populations. For example, the strategic engagement in multiple partnerships by individuals high in Machiavellianism, or the romantic connection improved and maintained through sending sexually explicit images, focusing away from assumptions that risky sexual behaviour is always rooted in reckless or antisocial tendencies. Thus, the findings encourage a more nuanced understanding of the Dark Triad in contemporary sexual relationships.

Applications

In terms of application, the findings highlight the need for sexual health interventions and programmes to move beyond risk-focused education. Interventions among young adults must include an understanding of the emotional, relational, and self-esteem-based reasons for the engagement with risky sexual behaviour. Rather than describing RSBs as simply risky or irrational, programmes could be more effective if they acknowledge the roles of emotional intimacy, trust, strategic relationship development, and pursuit of self-affirmation. For instance, promoting communication competencies, enhancing emotional intelligence, and helping with healthier ways of obtaining emotional and relational needs could reduce the practice of unhealthy sexual behaviour without excluding members. Tailoring the interventions to maintain these underlying incentives would likely enhance involvement, use, and long-term behaviour change among young adults with Dark Triad personality tendencies.

Strengths and Limitations

A strong point of this present research is that it employs a mixed-methods design which allows a deeper insight into how dark triad personality traits are related to risky sexual behaviours. Since previous research had lacked a thorough, multi-faceted analysis of this correlation, the current research offers new evidence and exploration of what drives these behaviours. Also, in spite of the sensitive nature of the topics explored, the research was conducted with ethical rigor; issuing trigger warnings, anonymity of participants, and sexual health resources being made available during debrief. Additionally, the study successfully recruited 122 participants, sufficient to confirm a medium effect size. Notably, over 20 to 40 participants provided detailed responses to each of the open-ended questions, which is a large number for qualitative research. Given that participant recruitment is typically one of the greatest challenges for psychological research, this success contributes to the study's reliability and richness of findings.

Regarding limitation, the participant sample was confined to Psychology undergraduate students at a single British university and this resulted in sample bias, limiting generalisability to other young adults, particularly those who are not university-educated. Later studies could enhance representativeness by sampling through quota sampling methods to ensure variation along significant demographics. Second, although this study explored several types of risky sexual behaviour, it did not include other areas such as alcohol and 'chemsex' (Malandain & Thibaut, 2023). Although the research assessed behaviour during the last six months, this is a relatively brief time span. A longitudinal study design would allow for investigation of change in behaviour over time, providing more robust evidence of potential causal relationships.

Summary

The present study sought to examine why individuals engage in risky sexual behaviours; unprotected sex, multiple sexual partners, and sending explicit sexual images, and whether these risky sexual behaviours are predicted by Dark Triad personality traits. Psychopathy was the only significant predictor, whereas Machiavellianism and narcissism showed weak correlations of risky sexual behaviours. The psychopathic relationship seems to be associated with immediate pleasure-seeking and thrill-seeking but implies distinctions between subclinical psychopathic tendencies and clinical psychopathy, particularly where acts were driven by establishing trust and not emotional alienation.

Machiavellianism weakly correlated with having multiple sexual partners and sending sexually explicit images, implying strategic goal-directed actions. However, the existence of emotional and relational motivations identified in individuals in the study counteracts stereotypes about Machiavellianism as emotionally cold in nature. Narcissism had no predictive association and was weakly correlated with unprotected sex and risky sexual behaviours, possibly explained by wanting to save their egoistic public image, or, in some cases, by selfish motives where unprotected sex, for some, provided a subjective sense of being safe.

Along with personality variables, situational and affect-based factors accounted for unsafe sex. In unprotected sex, multiple sexual partnerships, and sending explicit pictures, ideas emerged such as sexual pleasure, peer influence, and relationship attitudes were persistent across all three behaviours. Some patterns included unprotected sex as a result of spontaneity during "the heat of the moment," multiple sexual partners used as a form of obtaining

emotional connection, and sending explicit images only when both parties agree and reciprocate the behaviour.

Overall, the findings suggest that while Dark Triad traits contribute to understanding of risky sexual behaviours, they do not provide the whole explanation for motivational complexity. Emotional needs, strategic relationship goals, and circumstance-dependent spontaneity overlap with personality-based tendencies. Suggesting the necessity of considering both personality and situational factors in sexual decision-making among young adults. Reflecting back to the broader objectives of the research, it is evident that sexual activity amongst the young adult population is an ongoing dialogue between risk mitigation and meeting emotional and relational desire. Future research and interventions must remain sensitive to the balance between risk and emotional needs, facilitating sexual health programmes that respect individuals' choices while also addressing the underlying motivations for risky sexual behaviours. By supporting young adults and encouraging open access to sexual health resources, programmes can better promote both emotional wellbeing and safer sexual practices.

REFLEXIVITY

Due to the thematic analysis, I may have been biased in interpreting information around risky sexual behaviour, as the subject sample were students from my course. To combat this, I interpreted the codes and themes myself then presented them to my supervisor to gain a second opinion, and made an agreement and the data became finalised. We both realised that the majority of the responses demonstrated decision-making capabilities surrounding risky sexual behaviours, showing that the majority are not done through impulsive behaviour. Therefore, I made sure to use triangulation as a way to link quantitative and qualitative findings together, only if they can be justified to be linked.

Furthermore, once the data became clear that the majority of the motivations around risky sexual behaviours were not all negative, but thoughtful to be used for good. This changed my perspective around people's engagement with sex, despite being risky, it is sometimes used for good purpose.

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APPENDICES

Appendix A: Front page of the survey, showing study exploration, anonymity notice, and trigger warning

Sexual risk-taking and personality in UK university students

Welcome

Page 1 of 13

Thank you for signing up to this study.

This study will explore sexual risk-taking and personality in UK university students. The survey is anonymous. Please read the questions carefully and answer them as truthfully as possible.

Please note: This survey will discuss topics that some may find sensitive. The topics discussed will focus on risky sexual behaviours and your involvement in them (i.e. unprotected sex, multiple sexual partners and sending sexual explicit images).

If you do not think that you will feel comfortable taking part in a study with such a focus, please do consider not taking part.

Next

Appendix B: G*Power Analysis Table

Appendix C: Ethical approval from the Health, Biological and Psychological Sciences Research Ethics Committee

Application for Project Review Positive Opinion

Project Title	A mixed methods study exploring gender differences in sexual behaviours within UK university students
Project ID	2169
Chief Investigator	[REDACTED FOR CONFIDENTIALITY]

20 January 2025

The Health, Biological and Psychological Sciences Research Ethics Committee has reviewed the above application.

1. Ethical opinion

The Committee provides a positive ethical opinion on the above research project on the basis described in the application form and supporting documentation, subject to the conditions specified below.

2. Summary of ethics review

The study "A mixed methods study exploring gender differences in sexual behaviours within UK university students" will use undergraduate psychology students as participants. The goal is to establish the prevalence of risky sexual behaviours (e.g. unprotected sex, multiple sexual partners, sharing of sexually explicit imagery) amongst University students.

The study will use an online questionnaire. The questions are of a sensitive nature however the study will be online, it will be anonymous and the topic will be flagged to participants before participation. Thus I feel that any risk that participants may be embarrassed or upset by the questions is appropriately mitigated. Please ensure that the process of keeping participants anonymous is robust.

3. Conditions of the ethical opinion

Research Approval

Your project has also received a governance review to ensure that it is ready to start. This letter confirms that you are authorised by the University of Leicester to start the above named project.

The ethics approval is subject to the following conditions being met:

- Please ensure that the process of keeping participants anonymous is robust.
- You are expected to deliver the research project in accordance with the University's policies and procedures, which includes the University's [Research Code of Conduct](#) and the [Research Ethics Policy](#).

4. Reporting requirements

You are required to notify the Committee of:

- Significant [amendments](#) to the project
- [Serious breaches](#) of the protocol
- The [end of study report](#)

5. Use of application information

Details from your ethics application will be stored on the University systems. With your permission, the Committee may wish to use parts of the application in an anonymised format for training or sharing best practice. Please let me know if you do not want the application details to be used in this manner.

**Authorised by the Health, Biological and Psychological Sciences Research Ethics Committee
University of Leicester**

Appendix D: Risky Sexual Behaviour Questionnaire: Containing questions relating to the topics of unprotected sex, multiple sexual partners, and sending explicit sexual images.

5. In the past 6 months, I have engaged in sexual activity without using barrier methods of protection (e.g., condoms). *

- Always
- Often
- Sometimes
- Rarely
- Never

6. In the past 6 months, I have had unprotected sex with a casual partner. *

- Always
- Often
- Sometimes
- Rarely
- Never

7. In the past 6 months, I have chosen not to use barrier methods of protection (e.g., condoms) even when it was available. *

- Always
- Often
- Sometimes
- Rarely
- Never

8. In the past 6 months, I have engaged in unprotected sex despite knowing the risks involved. *

- Always
- Often
- Sometimes
- Rarely
- Never

9. In the past 6 months, I have had unprotected sex multiple times. *

- Always
- Often
- Sometimes
- Rarely
- Never

13. In the past 6 months, I have had multiple sexual partners. *

- Always
- Often
- Sometimes
- Rarely
- Never

14. In the past 6 months, I have engaged in sexual activity with different partners within short time frames. *

- Always
- Often
- Sometimes
- Rarely
- Never

15. In the past 6 months, I have actively sought multiple new sexual partners. *

- Always
- Often
- Sometimes
- Rarely
- Never

16. In the past 6 months, I have had overlapping sexual relationships with multiple people. *

- Always
- Often
- Sometimes
- Rarely
- Never

17. In the past 6 months, I have preferred short-term encounters over long-term relationships. *

- Always
- Often
- Sometimes
- Rarely
- Never

21. In the past 6 months, I have sent explicit sexual images or videos of myself to others. *

- Always
- Often
- Sometimes
- Rarely
- Never

22. In the past 6 months, I have shared explicit sexual content with people I have never met in person. *

- Always
- Often
- Sometimes
- Rarely
- Never

23. In the past 6 months, I have engaged in reciprocal sharing of sexual content with another individual. *

- Always
- Often
- Sometimes
- Rarely
- Never

24. In the past 6 months, I have engaged in sexting* with casual or new partners.

**the action or practice of sending sexually explicit photographs or messages via mobile phone **

- Always
- Often
- Sometimes
- Rarely
- Never

25. In the past 6 months, I have sent explicit sexual content of people other than myself to others. *

- Always
- Often
- Sometimes
- Rarely
- Never

Appendix E: Open-ended questions relating to unprotected sex, multiple sexual partners and sending explicit sexual images

10. What are the reasons why you have chosen to engage in unprotected sex? (10 words minimum) *

Your answer has to have at least 10 words and at most 2000 words

0 / 2000 words

11. How do you weigh the risks and benefits when deciding whether or not to use protection? (10 words minimum) *

Your answer has to have at least 10 words and at most 2000 words

0 / 2000 words

12. Would you engage in unprotected sex again? Please answer yes or no and explain why. (10 words minimum) *

Your answer has to have at least 10 words and at most 2000 words

0 / 2000 words

18. What factors influenced your decision to have multiple sexual partners? (10 words minimum) *

Your answer has to have at least 10 words and at most 2000 words

0 / 2000 words

19. Have any external influences (e.g., social media, dating culture, personal experiences) contributed to your approach toward having multiple sexual partners? (10 words minimum) *

Your answer has to have at least 10 words and at most 2000 words

0 / 2000 words

20. Would you engage in having more multiple sexual partners again? Please answer yes or no and explain why. (10 words minimum) *

Your answer has to have at least 10 words and at most 2000 words

0 / 2000 words

26. What motivates you to send explicit sexual images? (10 words minimum) *

Your answer has to have at least 10 words and at most 2000 words

0 / 2000 words

27. How do you decide whom to share explicit content with, and what factors influence that decision? (10 words minimum) *

Your answer has to have at least 10 words and at most 2000 words

0 / 2000 words

28. Would you engage in sending explicit sexual images again? Please answer yes or no and explain why. (10 words minimum) *

Your answer has to have at least 10 words and at most 2000 words

0 / 2000 words

Appendix F: SD-3 Questionnaire measuring Dark Triad Personality traits; psychopathy, narcissism and machiavellianism

29. How strongly do you agree with the following statements... *

[Clear selected](#)

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
It's not wise to tell your secrets.	<input type="radio"/>				
I like to use clever manipulation to get my way.	<input type="radio"/>				
Whatever it takes, you must get the important people on your side.	<input type="radio"/>				
Avoid direct conflict with others because they may be useful in the future.	<input type="radio"/>				
It's wise to keep track of information that you can use against people later.	<input type="radio"/>				
You should wait for the right time to get back at people.	<input type="radio"/>				
There are things you should hide from others to get ahead.	<input type="radio"/>				
Make sure your plans benefit you, not others.	<input type="radio"/>				
Most people can be manipulated.	<input type="radio"/>				
People see me as a natural leader.	<input type="radio"/>				
I enjoy being the center of attention.	<input type="radio"/>				
Many group activities tend to be dull without me.	<input type="radio"/>				
I know that I am special because everyone keeps telling me so.	<input type="radio"/>				

I like to get acquainted with important people.	<input type="radio"/>				
I feel embarrassed if someone compliments me.	<input type="radio"/>				
I have been compared to famous people.	<input type="radio"/>				
I am not an average person.	<input type="radio"/>				
This is an attention check, answer disagree	<input type="radio"/>				
I insist on getting the respect I deserve.	<input type="radio"/>				
I like to get revenge on authorities.	<input type="radio"/>				
I avoid dangerous situations.	<input type="radio"/>				
Payback needs to be quick and nasty.	<input type="radio"/>				
People who mess with me always regret it.	<input type="radio"/>				
I have gotten into trouble with the law.	<input type="radio"/>				
People often say I am out of control	<input type="radio"/>				
It's true I can be mean to others	<input type="radio"/>				
I enjoy having sex with people I hardly know	<input type="radio"/>				
I'll say anything to get what I want	<input type="radio"/>				

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Note. The questions would be randomised when initiated by participant

Questions 1 - 9: Measure Machiavellianism

Questions 10 - 17, 19: Measure Narcissism

Question 18 - Attention Checker

Questions 20 - 28: Measure Psychopathy

Appendix G: Participation Information Sheet in the survey

Sexual risk-taking and personality in UK university students

Participant Information Sheet

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You are being invited to take part in a research project. Before you decide whether or not to take part, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully.

The aim of this study is to explore the prevalence of different types of sexual behaviours (i.e. unprotected sex, sex with multiple partners, and the sharing of sexual images), and the potential link with personality traits through an online anonymous survey. You will be asked to read a number of descriptions of behaviours and indicate, on a scale 1 to 5, how much you have undertaken these behaviours in the last six months. You may then be asked some open-ended questions exploring your thoughts around your participation in these behaviours. Finally, you will be asked to complete a short personality scale. Overall, the survey should take 20 minutes.

The data collected as part of this study may be used, in part or in whole, for the writing of an educational project for an Undergraduate Degree. At no time would any personally identifiable data be published without consent.

What is the purpose of the research project?

The overarching aim of the research is to improve our understanding of risky sexual behaviour, and its drivers, on a university campus. The data collection for the full project will take place over the next month.

Why have I been invited to participate?

You have been invited to take part in this research project as first and second-year undergraduate students at the University of Leicester in exchange of EPR credits for your course.

Do I have to take part?

It is up to you to decide whether or not to take part in this research project. If you do decide to take part you will be given this information sheet along with a privacy notice that will explain how your data will be collected and used, and be asked to provide your consent to participate. If you decide to take part you are still free to withdraw at any time up to the point at which you submit your data. You can do this by closing the browser. Choosing to either take part or not take part in the research project will have no impact on your marks, assessments or future studies.

What will happen to me if I take part?

If you decide to take part, you will be asked to complete an online questionnaire. Completing these questions should take around 15-20 minutes. Once completed, you will be granted the EPR credits.

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

Taking part in this research study could potentially benefit others by providing more robust research relating to this field.

What data will you collect about me?

The data collected will be anonymous. You will be asked to provide your age and gender, as well as to provide answers to the survey on your participation (or not) in different types of sexual behaviour and the personality measure survey.

Will what I say in this research project be kept confidential?

All the information collected will be kept confidentially. The data will be collected anonymously, so no names will be linked with the data received.

How will you look after the data you collect about me?

We need to ensure that you understand what will happen to data we collect about you as well as your legal rights. This document is accompanied with a separate Privacy Notice providing further details. Your normal rights under the Data Protection Act and the General Data Protection Regulation apply. However, we need to manage your records in specific ways for the research project to be reliable. This means that we won't [always] be able to let you see or change the data we hold about you. You can stop being part of the research project at any time, without giving a reason, but we will keep information about you that we already have and continue to use this for the purposes of the research project as outlined here. At all times this research study will comply with the UK General Data Protection Regulations (2018).

What will happen to the results of the research project?

The results of the research project will be included within an Undergraduate dissertation project which will be submitted to the University for assessment. A summary of the findings will be available to you upon request. To request such findings please email:

What should I do if I want to take part?

You will be asked to complete an Informed Consent Form and to opt-in to a variety of research options by ticking the Yes or No box. This will confirm you understand how your data will be processed, protected and reviewed for research purposes.

Who is organising and funding the research project?

This research project is organised by [REDACTED FOR CONFIDENTIALITY] School of Psychology and Vision Sciences at the University of Leicester and is overseen by the [REDACTED FOR CONFIDENTIALITY]

What if something goes wrong?

In the very unlikely event of you being harmed by taking part in this research project, there are no special compensation arrangements. If you are harmed due to someone's negligence, then you may have grounds for legal action but you may have to pay for it.

Who has reviewed the research project?

This research project has been approved by the University of Leicester Research Ethics Committee.

Contact for Further Information

For further information on the study, please contact [REDACTED FOR CONFIDENTIALITY]

To raise any concerns or queries about the way in which this research project has been conducted, please contact the Chair of the University Research Ethics Committee on ethics@le.ac.uk.

If you require more GDPR data protection information then you can access this via the University's Information Assurance Services:

Information Assurance Services University of Leicester University Road Leicester LE1 7RH: +44 (0)116 229 7945E: dpo@le.ac

W: <https://www2.le.ac.uk/offices/ias/>

Thank you

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Appendix H: GDPR Information in the survey

Sexual risk-taking and personality in UK university students

GDPR Privacy Notice

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This Privacy Notice provides information about how the University of Leicester collects and uses your personal information when you take part in this research projects.

Please also refer to the Participant Information Sheet given to you for further details about the research project, what information will be collected about you, and how it will be used.

The University of Leicester will usually be the *Data Controller* of any data that you supply for this research. This means that we are responsible for looking after your information and using it properly. This means that the University will make the decisions on how your data is used and for what reasons. The exception to this is joint research projects, if this is applicable you will be informed on the Participant Information Sheet as to the other partner institution(s) who will also have responsibilities for looking after your information. You can access more information on this via the University's Information Assurance Services:

Information Assurance Services | University of Leicester | University Road Leicester LE1 7RH | T: +44 (0)116 229 7945 | E: ias@le.ac.uk | W: <https://www2.le.ac.uk/offices/ias>

Why do we need your data?

For an undergraduate research project.

University of Leicester's legal basis for collecting this data is:

Processing is necessary for the performance of a task in the public interest such as research.

If the university asks you for sensitive data such as; your racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, trade-union membership, data concerning health or sexual life, genetic/biometric data or criminal records, the University of Leicester will use these data because:

Processing is necessary for scientific or research in the public interest.

What type of data will the University of Leicester use?

Survey data (completed online)

Who will the University of Leicester share your data with?

The University of Leicester will not share your data with anyone. Only [REDACTED FOR CONFIDENTIALITY]

Will the University of Leicester transfer my data outside of the UK?

No

What rights do I have regarding my data held by the University of Leicester?

Your normal rights under the Data Protection Act and the General Data Protection Regulation apply. However, we need to manage your records in specific ways for the research project to be reliable. This means that we will not be able to let you see or change the data we hold about you.

You can stop being part of the research project as outlined in the Participant Information Sheet, without giving a reason, but we will keep information about you that we already have and continue to use this for the purposes of the research project as outlined in the Participant Information Sheet.

Where did the University of Leicester source my data from?

It will be collected from yourself only.

Are there any consequences of not providing the requested data?

There are no consequences of not providing data for this research. It is purely voluntary.

Will there be any automated decision making using my data?

There will be no use of automated decision making in scope of UK Data Protection and Privacy legislation.

How long will the University of Leicester keep my data?

In line with the law, we will only keep your data for as long as we need to so that we can fulfil our research objectives. Should the team wish to publish the research, the data will be stored on the R Drive for up to six years. If not, the data will be deleted from the CIs OneDrive three months after degree has been awarded.

Who can I contact if I have concerns?

In the event of any questions about the research project, please contact the researchers in the first instance. Please contact
[REDACTED FOR CONFIDENTIALITY]

If you have any concerns about the way in which the research project has been conducted, please contact the Chair of the University Research Ethics Committee at ethics@leicester.ac.uk.

The University of Leicester Data Protection Officer is:

Data Protection Officer
University of Leicester,
University Road, Leicester, LE1 7RH
0116 229 7640
DPO@le.ac.uk

For further details about information security, please contact the [Information Assurance Services](#) team.

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Appendix I: Consent Form in the survey

CONSENT FORM

Please read the questions carefully

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1. I confirm I have read and understand the participant information sheet (Version 1.2) for the above study and have had the opportunity to ask questions. *

- Yes
 No

2. I understand my participation is voluntary and I am free to withdraw at any time prior to submitting my data. I understand that, upon completing the survey, I will not be able to withdraw my data. *

- Yes
 No

3. I understand that at all time this research project will comply with the *General Data Protection Regulations (GDPR, 2018)* approved by the EU parliament on 14 April 2016 and passing into UK law effective from 25 May 2018 and that if I have any concerns, I know how I can contact the University of Leicester to raise these. *

- Yes
 No

4. I agree to take part in this research project. *

- Yes
 No

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Appendix J: Debrief section in the survey

DEBRIEF

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Thank you for taking part in this survey! Your time is very much appreciated.

The aim of this study is to explore the relationships between dark triad personality traits (i.e. psychopathy, narcissism and Machiavellianism) and risky sexual behaviours (specifically, partaking in unprotected sex, having multiple sexual partners and sending explicit sexual images). This survey will provide information as to the prevalence of risky sexual behaviours and explore whether it can be explained, in part, by personality traits .

For further information regarding this study, you can contact [REDACTED FOR CONFIDENTIALITY]

To raise any queries or concerns about the way in which this research project has been conducted, please contact the Chair of the University Ethics Committee on ethics@le.ac.uk

Support for sexual wellbeing:

Should you require any support, please do take note of these links.

Sexual Health & Wellbeing Support - <https://www.brook.org.uk/>

Leicester County Council Sexual Health - <https://www.leicestershire.gov.uk/health-and-wellbeing/sexual-health/get-advice-on-sexual-health-and-relationships>

Leicester Sexual Health - <https://leicestersexualhealth.nhs.uk/professionals/resources>

Free STI Testing Kit - <https://sh24.org.uk/orders/sti-test-kit/intro-sti>

Free Condoms in Leicester - <https://leicestersexualhealth.nhs.uk/c-card>

Contraception Advice and How To - <https://www.letstalkaboutit.nhs.uk/contraception/>

Sexual and Domestic Violence Support - <https://www.rflifelinks.co.uk/sexual-violence-crime/>

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Appendix K: Cronbach's Alpha assessing questions relating to Risky Sexual Behaviour and SD-3

Scale	<i>N</i>	Cronbach's α
Unprotected Sex (US)	5	.94
Multiple Sexual Partners (MSP)	5	.84
Explicit Sexual Images (ESI)	5	.81
Machiavellianism	9	.74
Narcissism	9	.75
Psychopathy	9	.75

Note. *N* refers to the number of questions in the scale. Cronbach's α refers to internal consistency reliability for each scale used in the study.

Appendix L: Multiple Linear Regression analysis for Output for Predicting Risky Sexual Behaviour (RSB)

Predictor	<i>B</i>	<i>SE</i>	β	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	95% CI (Lower)	95% CI (Upper)	Tolerance	VIF
(Intercept)	5.40	4.65		1.16	.25	-3.81	14.61		
Psychopathy Score	0.59	0.16	.35	3.62	< .001	0.03	0.92	0.77	1.30
Narcissism Score	0.23	0.14	.14	1.66	.10	-0.04	0.49	0.94	1.06
Machiavellianism Score	0.05	0.16	.03	0.28	.78	-0.27	0.36	0.74	1.36

Note. *B* = unstandardised coefficient. *SE* = standard error. β = standardised beta. CI = confidence interval. VIF = variance inflation factor.

Appendix M: Pearson's Correlation Analysis Between Risky Sexual Behaviours (RSB) and Dark Triad Personality Traits

Variable	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1. RSB Summary Score	-						
2. Unprotected Sex (US)	.86***	-					
3. Multiple Sexual Partners (MSP)	.58***	.24*	-				
4. Explicit Sexual Images (ESI)	.61***	.26**	.24**	-			
5. Machiavellianism	.23*	.15	.19*	.21*	-		
6. Narcissism	.20*	.19*	.08	.12	.24**	-	
7. Psychopathy	.38***	.27**	.32**	.26**	.48***	.13	-

Note. $p < .05$, $p < .01$, $p < .001$

Appendix N: Linearity testing via Residuals vs. Predicted Values plots

Risky Sexual Behaviour and Dark Triad Personality Traits:

Residuals vs. Predicted

Unprotected Sex (US):

Residuals vs. Predicted

Multiple Sexual Partners (MSP):

Residuals vs. Predicted

Explicit Sexual Images:

Residuals vs. Predicted

Appendix O: Q-Q Plots testing the Normality of Residuals

Risky Sexual Behaviour and Dark Triad Personality Traits:

Q-Q Plot Standardized Residuals

Unprotected Sex (US):

Q-Q Plot Standardized Residuals

Multiple Sexual Partners (MSP):

Q-Q Plot Standardized Residuals

Explicit Sexual Images (ESI):

Q-Q Plot Standardized Residuals

Appendix P: Collinearity Diagnostics for Predictors of Risky Sexual Behaviours

Risky Sexual Behaviours (RSB):

Predictor	Tolerance	VIF
Psychopathy	0.77	1.30
Narcissism	0.94	1.06
Machiavellianism	0.74	1.36

Note. Tolerance below .10 value and VIF value above 10 indicate breach of multicollinearity concerns (Field, 2016). All values in Appendix F are within the acceptable range.

Appendix Q: Durbin-Watson Statistical Analysis for Regression Model Predicting Risky Sexual Behaviours

Variable	Durbin-Watson
Risky Sexual Behaviours (RSB)	1.76
Unprotected Sex (US)	1.90
Multiple Sexual Partners (MSP)	1.84
Explicit Sexual Images (ESI)	2.01

Note. Values between 1.5 and 2.5 are considered acceptable independence of residuals (Field, 2016)

Appendix R: Influential Cases Identified via Regression Diagnostics for Risky Sexual Behaviour

Risky Sexual Behaviour (RSB):

Case Number	Standardised Residual	Observed Value	Predicted Value	Residual	Cook's Distance

Note. No influential cases were identified

Unprotected Sex (US):

Case Number	Standardised Residual	Observed Value	Predicted Value	Residual	Cook's Distance

Note. No influential cases were identified

Multiple Sexual Partners (MSP):

Case Number	Standardised Residual	Observed Value	Predicted Value	Residual	Cook's Distance
70	4.03	17	6.42	10.58	0.11
87	4.56	18	6.02	11.98	0.13
100	3.04	16	8.10	7.90	0.11

Note. Cook's Distance greater than 1 suggests strong influence, all values remain below 1 suggesting no extreme influence (Field, 2016).

Explicit Sexual Images (ESI):

Case Number	Standardised Residual	Observed Value	Predicted Value	Residual	Cook's Distance
34	5.28	25	8.90	16.10	0.31
69	3.20	15	5.32	9.68	0.15
93	3.92	20	8.32	11.68	0.36

Note. Cook's Distance greater than 1 suggests strong influence, all values remain below 1 suggesting no extreme influence (Field, 2016).

Appendix S: Quotes from Open-ended Questions relating to Unprotected Sex (US) being turned into codes

Unprotected Sex (US):

Quotes	Codes
<p>there is no risk of pregnancy so there is no need for protection</p>	<p>No risk of pregnancy seen as a reason to engage in unprotected sex</p>
<p>we both were tested before, and my partner said that's what they prefer and i didn't have an issue</p>	<p>Partners testing before having sex seen as a reason to engage in unprotected sex</p>
<p>I felt like it, no condoms available at the time.</p>	<p>Issue with availability of condom access</p>
<p>would feel better. heat of the moment</p>	<p>Having unprotected sex feels better especially when heat of the moment</p>
<p>There is a better feeling and it isn't something that often crosses my mind with my current partner</p>	<p>Unprotected sex feels better and not thinking about risks</p>
<p>I came off of the contraceptive pill, and me and my boyfriend kept forgetting to buy condoms.</p>	<p>People forgetting to buy protections</p>
<p>We tried unprotected sex for once when there isn't condoms available and we found out that it gives us a better experience.</p>	<p>Lack of condoms available resulted in unprotected sex and realised to be pleasurable</p>
<p>i only engage with my boyfriend so it's not as dangerous as sleeping with multiple people</p>	<p>Having sex with trusted partner is safer than multiple people</p>

<p>Barrier methods (condoms) do not stimulate me as much as unprotected ,</p> <p>barrier methods have also failed in the past (ripped condoms).</p> <p>There was not a lot of thought behind it, in the moment it felt okay.</p> <p>it felt right in the moment</p> <p>- i am on the implant so i know that pregnancy is not a risk factor.</p> <p>Because I am in a committed relationship and feel comfortable and secure with the idea.</p> <p>it was for pleasure choices for both partners and convenience</p> <p>I am in a long-term monogamous relationship</p> <p>where we have both been tested previously and found that we are both healthy/don't have any STI's.</p> <p>And as a queer couple our</p>	<p>Barrier methods are not sexually stimulating as unprotected sex</p> <p>Barrier methods have failed to work during sex</p> <p>Lack of thought behind sex resulted in unprotected sex</p> <p>Unprotected sex seen as right in the moment</p> <p>Risks of unprotected sex reduces due to being on coil</p> <p>Being in a relationship makes it more comfortable to have unprotected sex</p> <p>Unprotected sex is pleasurable and convenient for partners</p> <p>Only participating in unprotected sex because of being in a long-term monogamous relationship</p> <p>Partners testing and free of STIs is reason for unprotected sex</p> <p>Being LGBTQ+ results in difficulties with convenience with protection</p>
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<p>options for protective sex don't seem comfortable/ideal</p> <p>plus they are not as accessible as condoms for example.</p> <p>I track my cycles</p> <p>/I have a boyfriend so I have 1 consistent partner</p> <p>/barrier methods not as enjoyable</p> <p>I have a contraceptive implant, so I choose not to use a condom.</p> <p>I've only had unprotected sex when i first lost my virginity, ever since i have been on the pill (last 3 years),</p> <p>when I first was having unprotected sex, it was because i was too scared to ask my mum to take me to the GP to go onto the pill</p> <p>convenience of not using protection</p> <p>or ruining the mood by asking to use protection as well as spur of the moment</p> <p>Protection was likely not</p>	<p>Condoms seen as inaccessible for LGBTQ+ couples</p> <p>Tracking your cycle seen as a way to tackle unprotected sex</p> <p>A consistent partner seen as permissible for unprotected sex</p> <p>Barrier methods viewed as unenjoyable</p> <p>Not using condoms because of using other contraceptives</p> <p>Partaking in unprotected sex whilst taking the pill</p> <p>Partaking in unprotected sex because of fear for asking for contraceptives</p> <p>Unprotected sex seen as more convenient than using condoms</p> <p>Asking to use condoms in sex negatively impacts sexual mood</p> <p>Lack of availability of protection resulted in</p>
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<p>available at the time so instead of trying to find some i just engaged.</p>	<p>unprotected sex</p>
<p>because i have wanted to try it with my boyfriend</p>	<p>Curiosity to try unprotected sex with partner</p>
<p>didn't have access to the right condoms</p>	<p>Not being able to access condoms</p>
<p>so waited until i was able to have the iud fitted As I am on birth control</p>	<p>Having birth control allows person to partake in unprotected sex</p>
<p>and my partner is my long-term boyfriend,</p>	<p>Only engaging in unprotected sex with someone they are in a relationship with</p>
<p>we feel it is no longer necessary as we are both tested and</p>	<p>Protected sex seen as unnecessary because of STI testing</p>
<p>do not have other sexual partners.</p>	<p>Engages with unprotected sex due to having no multiple partners</p>
<p>Either no condoms available at the time,</p>	<p>Lack of availability of protection resulted in unprotected sex</p>
<p>or just a spur of the moment thing without thinking about protection.</p>	<p>Not thinking about protection in sex due to spur of the moment</p>
<p>Because I don't associate with people who are going around having sex with anyone. I am in a relationship where it is me and him only.</p>	<p>Only having sex with partner to avoid association with sexually active population</p>
<p>I'm also on the pill anyways but</p>	<p>Being on the pill seen as a reason to engage in unprotected sex</p>

<p>I know it's still important to not readily available in the moment and depends on who it is</p> <p>Increased trust and intimacy feels higher when you don't use barrier protection feels better, with trusted partner, and using other forms of contraception I am in a long term relationship with my partner, neither of us have a sexually transmitted infections/diseases and we are taking other measures to prevent pregnancy.</p> <p>It's with my partner, and we've been together for 3 years so I know we are both clean and there is no risk to either of us.</p> <p>I also am on the pill so i'm not likely to get pregnant.</p> <p>It also feels better without a condom.</p> <p>i was comfortable with my partner</p> <p>and we believe it feels better I was giving oral and deemed the risk to be minimal</p> <p>the feeling of a condom is not</p>	<p>Lack of availability of condoms during the moment</p> <p>Unprotected sex improves intimacy and trust with partner</p> <p>Taking several measures to reduce risks of unprotected sex</p> <p>Reassured that both parties are STI free</p> <p>Being on the pill reduces risk of pregnancy</p> <p>The feeling of unprotected sex better than with a condom</p> <p>Feeling comfortable to have unprotected sex with partner</p> <p>Only engage in unprotected sex because it was only oral</p> <p>The feeling of a condom is different to not using one</p>
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<p>as pleasurable compared to doing it without.</p> <p>It's never really something me and my boyfriend think about when having sex.</p> <p>It feels better</p> <p>and I trust the person I am engaging in it with.</p> <p>because i don't feel the need to use protection, i think im infertile</p> <p>We are both on PrEP</p> <p>and often take STI tests</p> <p>i was in a long term relationship with the person and trusted him very deeply, he also 'pulled out' everytime</p> <p>i was in a long term relationship and there were no health issues i am a lesbian</p> <p>and we have both been tested</p> <p>I have the implant so i feel comfortable not using barrier forms of protection.</p> <p>It was with my boyfriends so I wasn't worried about getting anything</p> <p>It is more convenient (the price</p>	<p>Not thought about between both parties to use a condom</p> <p>Unprotected sex is viewed to feel better</p> <p>Trust is involved to engage in unprotected sex</p> <p>Thinking infertility is a reason to partake in unprotected sex</p> <p>Using PrEP to reduce risks of STIs</p> <p>Often taking STI tests to reduce risk of unprotected sex</p> <p>Trusting your partner to reduce risks of unprotected sex</p> <p>Being lesbian thought to reduce some risks of unprotected sex</p> <p>Testing for STIs reduce risk of unprotected sex</p> <p>Feeling comfortable to partake in unprotected sex due to other forms of contraceptives</p> <p>Lack of worry for catching risks of STIs due to being with a partner</p> <p>Price of condoms makes unprotected sex more convenient</p>
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<p>of condoms is insane)</p> <p>and it feels good</p> <p>Barrier methods were not available at the time of intercourse</p> <p>only risky if there is a risk of pregnancy</p> <p>or infection if they haven't been tested then i won't engage,</p> <p>it's not worth it. even sometimes with a condom i don't like the risk</p> <p>do I trust him, ovulation. Plan b, would he just pull out</p> <p>If I know the person and if the situation is one off or recurring and how much I trust the person</p> <p>I know its more beneficial to both me and him to use protection, but sometimes i forget about the pros and cons and we just get carried away in the moment.</p> <p>I know that there are more risks than benefits on unprotected sex. I personally think that the risks are higher and I am unable to handle if I am pregnant.</p>	<p>The feeling of unprotected sex is seen as good</p> <p>During intercourse, barrier methods were not accessible</p> <p>Main worry of risk of unprotected sex is getting pregnant</p> <p>Will not engage in unprotected sex if not previously tested</p> <p>Worried that using condoms during sex can be still be risky</p> <p>Taking several methods to avoid risks during unprotected sex</p> <p>Choosing whether to engage in unprotected sex based on trust</p> <p>Knowing the benefits of a condom but heat of the moment results in no condom use</p> <p>Worried about risks of unprotected sex such as pregnancy</p> <p>Engaging in unprotected sex provides more</p>
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<p>However, it does gives us a better experience.</p> <p>Because we are determined with one partner, therefore, we understand each other's needs and boundaries. He understands that I will be very anxious if he does last minute pullouts and he knows that it could be risky. Thus, he would pullout before feeling his precum and use his hands to help him. Other than that, when it is almost/during my ovulation period, I would tell him to use condoms as protection as the chances of pregnancy is higher. This would lower the chances of risks, I'd say.</p> <p>I'm aware there are alot more risks but it's just the spur of the moment</p> <p>I always assess the risks before considering unprotected sex, especially based on how close within my fertility window I am compared to on my period. Despite this, I am still always aware of the risks of unprotected sex, no matter the benefit.</p> <p>It depends on how well i know</p>	<p>pleasure</p> <p>Engaging in unprotected sex because of trust with partner</p> <p>Only using a condom during sex when ovulating</p> <p>Heat of the moment during sex results increase chance of unprotected sex</p> <p>Partaking in unprotected sex based on their fertility cycle</p> <p>Knowledgeable of the risks of unprotected sex</p> <p>Partaking in unprotected sex based on personal circumstances</p>
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<p>the person i am having sex with and feel safe to do so.</p> <p>i think that it is more enjoyable without protection and tend to be selective about who i sleep with - however if they are sleeping with other people i am more likely to think about using protection</p> <p>I take into consideration the phase of my cycle and likelihood of the risks.</p> <p>I know I am safe with my partner and</p> <p>make decisions only when I am not under the influence of alcohol, etc.</p> <p>i know there are actions to take afterwards that would help</p> <p>The risk for us seems to be minimised due to being tested previously,</p> <p>being in a monogamous relationship and trusting that we both remain faithful. We compare this to the benefits which is continuing as we are - not having to spend money on protection that we have only heard complaints about (when it comes to practicality)</p>	<p>Engaging in unprotected sex provides more pleasure</p> <p>Having multiple sexual partners results in higher chance of using protection during sex</p> <p>Tracking your cycle before engaging in unprotected sex</p> <p>Engaging in unprotected sex because of trust with partner</p> <p>Making decisions to engage in unprotected sex when sober</p> <p>Having knowledge of what to do after partaking in unprotected sex</p> <p>Being tested reduces risks of unprotected sex</p> <p>Being in a monogamous relationship improves trust in sex</p> <p>Avoiding spending on protection due to bad experiences with them</p>
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<p>and trying it out when it doesn't seem comfortable or ideal.</p> <p>If i am fertile or potentially ovulating I would use protection</p> <p>If I feel comfortable enough with that partner, especially if I trust them.</p> <p>benefits-as bad as it sounds, boys say they enjoy it more (without a condom) and I've had a boy refuse to put one on</p> <p>depending where i am on my menstrual cycle and risks of pregnancy I dont really think about it.</p> <p>I have never had a health or pregnancy scare so I dont consider it often</p> <p>how it feels versus what i will have to do to ensure not to have a pregnancy well the benefits are feeling that intimacy</p> <p>and the risks arent really that bad because you can take the morning after pill</p> <p>While I understand the risks, as</p>	<p>Using protection seen as uncomfortable and inconvenient</p> <p>Only using a condom during sex with ovulating</p> <p>Engaging in unprotected sex because of trust with partner</p> <p>Partaking in unprotected sex because others prefer it</p> <p>Not worried about unprotected sex unless ovulating</p> <p>Engages in unprotected sex because no past experience of becoming pregnant</p> <p>Engaging in unprotected sex due to experience feeling of intimacy</p> <p>Risk of unprotected sex can be solved with morning after pill</p>
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<p>mentioned earlier neither me nor my partner carry STDs/STIs and we are each others sole sexual partners, so protection doesn't factor in that department.</p>	<p>Protection in sex seen as unnecessary due to regular testing and being sole partners to each other</p>
<p>As I have been on long-term birth control for years (coil) we also don't deem it necessary to prevent pregnancy. Also i</p>	<p>Unprotected sex is practiced because already using a contraception (coil)</p>
<p>t is against our sexual preference . However if I was to engage in this with a casual partner I would definitely use any and all forms of protection available</p>	<p>Protected sex seen as against sexual preferences</p>
<p>I don't really weight out the risks and benefits, sometimes i will think about it, but most of the time i risk it.</p>	<p>Accepting the risk when engaging in unprotected sex</p>
<p>I wouldn't just have sex with a random person so I don't need to worry about that whether you are ovulating or not, if you know the person</p>	<p>Only having unprotected sex with someone you know, not a random person</p>
<p>and are going out you are aware they do not carry sexually transmitted diseases</p>	<p>Partaking in unprotected sex only if you are aware they do not have STIs</p>
<p>How long I've known the person being aware that they're clean of unwanted diseases and trust major parts</p>	<p>Trust is a major factor in partaking in unprotected sex</p>

<p>of that. Always try to use barrier method when having a one night stand however because the circumstances I don't necessarily think about it first which is really silly of me.</p>	<p>Not thinking about the circumstances of unprotected sex</p>
<p>protection always used if risk of pregnancy/anxiety around risk of pregnancy, with trusted partner protection is not used for sexual activity</p>	<p>Engaging in unprotected sex because of trust with partner</p>
<p>without risk of pregnancy due to no risk of infection, pleasure would not outweigh risk of pregnancy</p>	<p>The risk of pregnancy outweighs the pleasure benefits of unprotected sex</p>
<p>Risks of infection or disease is the most important, risk of pregnancy, pleasure is least important but if the other risks are reduced then this is important in a relationship</p>	<p>Knowing the risk of disease of unprotected sex impacts the engagement in unprotected sex</p>
<p>I look at my likelihood of getting pregnant and catching a sexual disease, and if it's unlikely/practically 0% chance then I won't use protection.</p>	<p>Only engage in unprotected sex if risk of pregnancy and disease are low</p>
<p>if i have known them for a while and if we are both comfortable with the idea I use protection on anal but not oral, I research the risks accordingly</p>	<p>Engaging in unprotected sex if people know each other for some time</p>

<p>beforehand Depending on the partner I would pose the questions to them to avoid any risks such as if they have done it with anyone else before me and</p>	<p>Asking questions to partner to determine whether to engage in unprotected sex</p>
<p>if so have they had any problems prior to this encounter.</p>	<p>Exploring if having sex with other people is a problem with engaging in unprotected sex</p>
<p>It isn't something we consider in the moment, and we're always careful I do not really think about it in the moment</p>	<p>Unprotected sex chances increase because of lack of concern for protection</p>
<p>i'm with my boyfriend so unprotected sex feels safe as we're both clean</p>	<p>Unprotected sex seen as safe if with a partner that is "clean"</p>
<p>Neither of us can get pregnant because we are both men so there is less need for protection</p>	<p>Lack of worry for protection as the couple is LGBTQ+ therefore cannot get pregnant</p>
<p>and there is no risk of either of us getting an STI because we don't sleep with other people risks</p>	<p>Catching STIs from unprotected sex is low if not engage with other people sexually</p>
<p>would be getting pregnant of course but there are ways to negate that even without using</p>	<p>Taking several methods to avoid pregnancy during unprotected sex</p>

<p>protection, like pulling out, plan bs or even abortions if it gets to that point there are few benefits but the risks could be avioded in multiple ways no risks apart from UTI as we have been together for over 1 year If i feel comfortable and trust the person enough to do so.</p> <p>If the person has been tested and if I am on birth control</p> <p>Ask the other person if they have tested (for STIs), if so then potentially request proof I think about precautions I can take after intercourse has taken place</p> <p>yes because i have nothing to worry about so it is okay yes because i think it's normal in a relationship to have unprotected sex no.</p> <p>I plan to get some non hormonal contraception like IUD</p> <p>Yes, I have a partner who I trust and beleive it is safe with them No, because</p> <p>the anxiety i felt after it wondering if i could possibly be pregnant is not worth it.</p>	<p>Engaging in unprotected sex because of trust with partner</p> <p>Having unprotected sex only if tested and on a contraception</p> <p>Requesting proof of testing for STI before having unprotected sex</p> <p>Engaging in unprotected sex due to lack of worry</p> <p>Viewing unprotected sex is normal in relationship</p> <p>Planning to use contraceptives (IUD) in the future</p> <p>Feeling safe to have sex with partner due to trust</p> <p>Worrying about becoming pregnant due to sex</p>
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<p>Yes, I would engage in unprotected sex again because I have a stable partner and we know each other very well.</p>	<p>Engaging in unprotected sex because of trust with partner</p>
<p>There are only two occasions that I would not engage in unprotected sex: before/during my ovulation period or a month before summer holiday because I would have to go home and we're not allowed to do abortion.</p>	<p>Engaging in sex due to personal circumstances based on ones cycle or event</p>
<p>i would like to say no but probably yes because i don't think as much as i should</p>	<p>Having sex due to impulsive thinking to engage</p>
<p>Yes, as I have previously found it increases the experience in relation to satisfaction.</p>	<p>Having unprotected sex increases satisfactions</p>
<p>However, I would not engage in unprotected sex on as much of a regular basis.</p>	<p>Making a choice not to engage in unprotected sex on a regular basis</p>
<p>yes - It depends on the person and whether or not we are in a committed relationship yes - if they are a partner i trust then i do not see a big issue with doing so Yes, because I feel secure to regardless of potential risks. I feel confident to handle any situation I may find myself in alongside my</p>	<p>Not seeing an issue in engaging in unprotected sex because with trusted partner</p>

<p>partner</p> <p>yes i would but instead i would take contraceptives such as the pill or implant</p> <p>Yes, I think that they likelihood of an STI is low in my relationship as we have both been tested before having entering the relationship and trust that we will remain faithful to each other (not introducing risk in my perception).</p> <p>Yes, it is more enjoyable,</p> <p>but I make sure I have tracked my cycles accurately first Yes beacuse I'm now in a relationship so we both know we don't have STI and I trust him.</p> <p>no, too much risk, causes stress and if to get pregangt, an abortion could be potentially traumatic</p> <p>yes, again because of convenience of where we are and how accessible</p>	<p>Feeling confident in any situation because with a trusted partner</p> <p>Prefer to have unprotected sex with a contraception installed</p> <p>Expecting little chance of STI due to monogamy in a relationship</p> <p>Expecting trust in a relationship by being faithful to each other</p> <p>Seeing unprotected sex as more enjoyable than protected sex</p> <p>Tracking your cycle before engaging in unprotected sex</p> <p>Expecting no STIs due to being in a monogamous relationship</p> <p>Finding an aborting scary and traumatic</p> <p>Engaging in unprotected sex is seen as</p>
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<p>contraception is, as well as mood during</p> <p>Yes as i have had no issues so far so i see no reason to not continue</p> <p>yes, because i feel closer to my partner without protection</p> <p>yes, i am fine with having a child with the person im with despite it not being preferred</p> <p>Yes but only with my boyfriend, not with a casual sexual partner.</p> <p>Yes, i haven't experienced any issues yet. And worst case scenarios can always be resolved.</p> <p>Yh bec I don't need to worry about stds and I'm on the pill in the future if you want a child? depends on the situation Yes, as a woman I prefer it. There's a level of intimacy and connection you have with an individual from not using protection.</p> <p>yes, if I was at a point where pregnancy would no longer be a major concern (+ still with trusted partner)</p>	<p>convenient</p> <p>Engaging in sex depends on how accessible contraception is</p> <p>Continuing unprotected sex due to no past bad experiences with unprotected sex</p> <p>Engaging in unprotected sex provides closeness in a relationship</p> <p>Accepting a child as a consequence of unprotected sex despite being not preferred</p> <p>Only engaging in unprotected sex with someone they are in a relationship with</p> <p>Knowing consequences of unprotected sex can be resolved</p> <p>Lack of worry for catching STIs and being on a contraceptive</p> <p>Preferring unprotected sex increases closeness and intimacy with a person</p> <p>Only engaging in unprotected sex with it did not result in pregnancy and with trusted</p>
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<p>With my current partner I would, this is because it is more convenient and enjoyable for us Yes - with my partner. However, if it was with someone random then I would never have unprotected sex as I don't know if they have any diseases.</p> <p>yes im in a relationship so we trust each other</p> <p>Yes for the examples given previously (I.e. when giving oral) Yes, as previously stated in my answer it feels nicer doing it unprotected and i also feel more connected to my partner.</p> <p>Yes, because I'm in a committed relationship so there's no risk in my opinion of getting any form of sexual disease</p> <p>Yes because it feels better and I trust the person</p> <p>yes because i and my partner get checked and stay clean</p> <p>Yes because condoms are too much effort just for them to split etc yes if it was with the same person, no in the future if its not with them.</p> <p>yes if im still with my partner no if not maybe</p> <p>yes, there are very minimal risks</p>	<p>partner</p> <p>Having unprotected sex with partner is convenient and enjoyable</p> <p>Not having unprotected sex with a random person due to fear of catching diseases</p> <p>Being in a relationship increases trust to engage in unprotected sex</p> <p>Engaging in unprotected sex provides pleasure</p> <p>Engaging in unprotected sex provides closeness in a relationship</p> <p>Not seeing an issue in engaging in unprotected sex because of a trusted partner</p> <p>Engaging in unprotected sex provides more pleasure</p> <p>Both parties engage in unprotected sex by doing regular STI testing</p> <p>Having a bad experience with protection in sex due to condom splitting</p> <p>Only engaging in unprotected sex with someone they are in a relationship with</p>
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<p>for me. my partner and i are long term and clean.</p> <p>Yes because i'm in a committed relationship with someone that i trust No , it's not worth getting pregnant or any infections</p> <p>No, I do not want to have a baby yet</p> <p>Yes but only with a trusted partner and if no contraception is available</p>	<p>Expecting minimal risk with unprotected sex because of being in a monogamous relationship</p> <p>Engaging in unprotected sex because of trust with partner</p> <p>Engaging in unprotected because of trust with partner</p> <p>Engaging in unprotected sex because of no access to contraceptives</p>
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Appendix T: Codes from Open-ended Questions relating to Unprotected Sex (US) being turned into subthemes

Unprotected Sex:

CODES	SUBTHEME
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Feeling safe to have sex with partners due to trust ● Engaging in unprotected sex because of trust with partner ● Not seeing an issue in engaging in unprotected sex because of a trusted partner ● Feeling confident in any situation because of a trusted partner ● Expecting trust in a relationship by being faithful to each other ● Expecting little chances of STI due to monogamy in a relationship ● Being in a relationship increases trust to engage in unprotected sex ● Choosing whether to engage in unprotected sex based on trust ● Only engaging in unprotected sex with someone they are in a relationship with ● Trust is a major factor in partaking in unprotected sex ● Being in a monogamous relationship improves trust in sex ● Having sex with a trusted partner is safer than multiple people ● A consistent partner seen as permissible for unprotected sex ● Trusting your partner to reduce risks of unprotected sex 	<p>Trust in Relationships as a Justification for Unprotected Sex</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Expecting no STIs due to being in a monogamous relationship ● Engaging in sex depends on how accessible contraception is ● Worrying about becoming pregnant due to sex ● Not having unprotected sex with a random person due to fear of catching diseases ● Will not engage in unprotected sex if not previously tested ● Knowledgeable of the risks of unprotected sex ● Knowing the risk of disease of unprotected sex impacts the engagement of unprotected sex ● Only engage in unprotected sex if risk of pregnancy and disease are low ● Engaging in unprotected sex if people know each other for some time ● Asking questions to partner to determine whether to engage in unprotected sex ● Requesting proof of testing for STI before having unprotected sex ● Catching STIs from unprotected sex is low if not engaging with other people sexually ● Taking several methods to avoid pregnancy during unprotected sex ● Partners testing before having sex is seen as a reason to engage in unprotected sex ● Taking on several methods to avoid risks during unprotected sex ● Unprotected sex seen as safe if with a partner that is "clean" ● Using PrEP to reduce risks of STIs ● Often taking STI tests to reduce risk of unprotected sex 	<p>Perceived Risk and Risk Reduction Strategies</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Having unprotected sex increases satisfaction ● Seeing unprotected sex as more enjoyable than protected sex ● Engaging in unprotected sex provides closeness in a relationship ● Preferring unprotected sex increases closeness and intimacy with a person ● Engaging in unprotected sex provides more pleasure 	<p>Preference for Unprotected Sex</p>

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The feeling of unprotected sex is better than with a condom • The feeling of a condom is different from not using one • Unprotected sex is viewed to feel better • Barrier methods are not sexually stimulating as unprotected sex • Unprotected sex feels better and not thinking about risks • The feeling of unprotected sex is seen as good • Unprotected sex is pleasurable and convenient for partners • Using protection seen as uncomfortable and inconvenient 	(Enjoyment, Intimacy, and Convenience)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engaging in unprotected sex is seen as convenient • Engaging in unprotected sex because of no access to contraception • Engaging in unprotected sex only if tested and on a contraception • Lack of condoms available resulted in unprotected sex and realized to be pleasurable • Lack of availability of protection resulted in unprotected sex • Lack of availability of condoms during the moment • People forgetting to buy protection • Not being able to access condoms • Issue with availability of condom access • Price of condoms makes unprotected sex more convenient • Condoms seen as inaccessible for LGBTQ+ couples • Being LGBTQ+ results in difficulties with convenience with protection • Protection in sex seen as unnecessary due to regular testing and being sole partners to each other 	Practical and Situational Factors
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Having sex due to impulsive thinking to engage • Knowing the benefits of a condom but heat of the moment results in no condom use • Heat of the moment during sex results increase chance of unprotected sex • Not thinking about protection in sex due to spur of the moment • Not thought about between both parties to use condoms • Unprotected sex seen as right in the moment • Lack of thought behind sex resulted in unprotected sex 	Influence of Impulsivity and "Heat of the Moment" Decisions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowing consequences of unprotected sex can be resolved • Accepting a child as a consequence of unprotected sex despite not being preferred • Risk of unprotected sex can be solved with morning after pill • Accepting the risk when engaging in unprotected sex • Finding an abortion scary and traumatic • Being tested reduces risk of unprotected sex • Feeling comfortable to partake in unprotected sex due to other forms of contraceptives • Feeling comfortable to have unprotected sex with partner 	Psychological Comfort and Reassurance in Unprotected Sex
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prefer to have unprotected sex with a contraception installed • Planning to use contraceptives (IUD) in the future • Tracking your cycle before engaging in unprotected sex • Only using a condom during sex when ovulating • Not worried about unprotected sex unless ovulating • Being on the pill reduces risk of pregnancy • Partaking in unprotected sex whilst taking the pill 	Use of Alternative Contraceptive Methods

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Partaking in unprotected sex because already using a contraception (coil) ● Being on the pill seen as a reason to engage in unprotected sex 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Continuing unprotected sex due to no past bad experiences with unprotected sex ● Only engaging in unprotected sex with it did not result in pregnancy and with a trusted partner ● Having a bad experience with protection in sex due to condom splitting ● Barrier methods have failed to work during sex ● Avoiding spending on protection due to bad experiences with them ● Having knowledge of what to do after partaking in unprotected sex ● Exploring if having sex with other people is a problem when engaging in unprotected sex ● Engages in unprotected sex because no past experience of becoming pregnant 	<p>Previous Experience and Learned Behaviour</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Partaking in unprotected sex because others prefer it ● Asking to use condoms in sex negatively impacts sexual mood ● Protected sex seen as unnecessary because of STI testing ● Only having sex with partner to avoid association with sexually active population ● Partaking in unprotected sex because of fear for asking for contraceptives 	<p>External Social Influences</p>

Appendix U: Subthemes from Open-ended Questions relating to Unprotected Sex (US) being turned into Themes

SUBTHEMES	FINAL THEME
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Trust in Relationships as a Justification for Unprotected Sex ● Preference for Unprotected Sex (Enjoyment, Intimacy, and Convenience) 	Trust and Relationship Dynamics
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Perceived Risk and Risk Reduction Strategies ● Psychological Comfort and Reassurance in Unprotected Sex ● Use of Alternative Contraceptive Methods 	Risk Perception and Decision-Making
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Influence of Impulsivity and "Heat of the Moment" Decisions ● Previous Experiences and Learned Behaviour 	Psychological and Behavioural Factors
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Practical and Situational Factors ● External Social Influences 	Situational and External Influences

Appendix V: Quotes from Open-ended Questions relating to Multiple Sexual Partners (MSP) being turned into Codes

Multiple Sexual Partners (MSP):

Quotes	Codes
the thrill of it has made me enjoy it so much	Gaining thrill from having sex with multiple people is enjoyable
It was not a conscious decision,	Decision to have sex with multiple people was not conscious
i went through a breakup and then wanted to enjoy myself with a new person.	Having sex with new people helps overcome break ups
I went through a breakup so naturally ended up sleeping with a new individual	Break up naturally led to having sex with other people
there were no influences as i didn't seek them out it just happened that way.	No influence to seek new sexual partners and it happened in the moment
ive slept with three, 2 boyfriends and one one night stand,	Feeling comfortable to have sex with multiple people
i think more an emotional connection i prefer	Enjoys the emotional connection from sex with partners
Not committed enough to one person,	Do not enjoy the commitment to one person

<p>and i'm young and want to have fun.</p>	<p>Prefers to explore their fun interests at a young age</p>
<p>was because it was a new guy i was interested in and had stopped talking to the previous one</p>	<p>Moving on person to person for sexual interests</p>
<p>Commuting to and from uni it's a situation where you have one up there one down there and the fact that men don't want to seem to settle down any more so why should I restrict myself for a person who can't commit to me?</p>	<p>Adapting to environments as people do not enjoy settling for one person</p> <p>Not interested in a romantic relationship</p>
<p>Don't have the time and energy for a relationship.</p>	<p>Short time frames at university makes romantic relationships pointless</p>
<p>No point being in a relationship when university is such a short period of time and I'm moving away afterwards.</p>	<p>Scheduling is not flexible in romantic relationships</p>
<p>Long term relationship ruin my daily routine because I change it around when I can see them,</p>	<p>Lack of structure in routines impacts mood negatively</p>
<p>I get unhappy/ low mood when my routine is not met.</p>	<p>Having sex with the same person can be boring and lacks excitement</p>
<p>Meeting someone on a night out and having sex is exciting, one person can get boring, I</p>	

<p>get bored after a few times having sexual with the sims person.</p>	
<p>It's difficult to find someone I actually really enjoy having sex with Usually if I feel the desire or feel lonely in myself</p>	<p>Difficult to find a person who fulfills sexual pleasure and enjoyment</p>
<p>I like to have a change and not be stuck to one person</p>	<p>Enjoying the control of changing the people to have sex with</p>
<p>i don't even know but i guess it is fun</p>	<p>Having sex with multiple is seen as moderately fun</p>
<p>The ability to find someone that makes me feel sexually fulfilled</p>	<p>Having sex with multiple people increases chances of finding sexual fulfillment</p>
<p>It was within different time periods so I felt comfortable with the other person yes i think a of influences have influenced me that multiple partners are better to experience in order to see who is the right one for you and to be able to find your preferences you need to explore first before setting your heart down into one person for the rest of your life.</p>	<p>Having multiple sexual partners can help the right person for you</p>
<p>I think so, going through a breakup changed my behaviours and perspectives as</p>	<p>Having multiple sexual partners allows to find the person who you can settle with romantically</p> <p>Facing a break from romance changes perspectives on sexual partnerships</p>

well as the dating culture of our generation.

I think dating culture as well as my personal experiences have been influential it is about personal experiences for me and dating culture I would say friends, when. You've broken up with a boy, they want you to get over him so by sleeping with someone that potentially helps

I've been in one bad relationship, so since then i don't feel ready to commit again not necessarily dating culture, was just a guy i liked and it naturally occurred was not related to us going to the stage of dating

I feel it has affected a lot of peoples interpretation of what a stable relationship looks like social media has encouraged the low commitment Situationship concept and it's upsetting and hurting a lot of people and I think we've all become victims of it because it's not normal

Being bullied as a child made me believe I was very unattractive and I feed off the

Having multiple sexual partners is a matter of personal preference

Sleeping with other people helps to overcome break ups

Bad experience with romantic relationships led to not seeking romantic relationships again

Social media creating concepts of situationships

Having multiple sexual partners provides attention to the person

<p>attention I get from other people. They made me feel like I'm attractive and wanted No (inserting random text here due to the 10 word limit) I am not from this city so I am used to my hometown's environment with the individuals I have been surrounded by so I tend to actively search for those similar to such.</p> <p>yes it does because it seems normal when it is not</p> <p>Yes, I think my past experiences may have had an impact I would say dating culture and personal experience had influenced me Yes because i feel conditioned to do so and i enjoy it</p> <p>yes - i do not think it is of much importance how many people i sleep with as long as it feels right to me.</p> <p>Yes - it depends on my circumstances and what makes me happy in the moment i haven't had multiple partners simultaneously and</p>	<p>Having multiple sexual partners improves self-esteem</p> <p>Seeking multiple sexual partners with similar interests</p> <p>Viewing the concept of multiple sexual partners as a mix of positives and negatives</p> <p>Past personal experiences impacted views on relationship concepts</p> <p>Conditioned to have multiple sexual partners and seeing it as enjoyable</p> <p>Having multiple sexual partners is not a problem as long as it is enjoyable</p> <p>Having multiple sexual partners is circumstantial as long as its enjoyable</p>
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<p>would not want to do it in the future</p> <p>yes, if i was to not have a boyfriend i think i probably would just because its a bit of fun and your young</p> <p>yes, life is too short to not have fun when you want to. and taking risks is sometimes fun</p> <p>Yes, I have been in scenarios where I've saved myself for someone who only half commits to me and it's been a big regret that I didn't allow myself freedom and take things at face value. It's one of those scenarios where if a man can do it so should I</p> <p>Yes, it's fun, exciting, get to have sex on my own time, when I want it without having any commitment</p> <p>Yes, whilst I would prefer seeing previous partners too, I think it's enjoyable to experience new partners too where we do not want to get attached to each other No as the thrill is starting to dry out and I am thinking to settle for one person yes but i wish i</p>	<p>Having multiple sexual partners can be experimented at a young age and is fun</p> <p>Having multiple sexual partners is a personal fun of choice</p> <p>Having multiple sexual partners allows more freedom</p> <p>Having multiple sexual partners is influenced by breaking gendered norms</p> <p>Having multiple sexual partners is personally convenient and fun</p> <p>Having multiple sexual partners reduces the issue of commitment responsibility</p> <p>Having sex with other people can be seen as a new experience</p> <p>Wishing for a personal choice to experience sexual preferences with other people</p>
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could say no as that would be better

No, I am in a happy committed relationship so don't want to do this. Only within different time periods, I don't believe in overlapping sexual partners

Having multiple sexual partners is an issue if within different time periods

Appendix W: Codes from Open-ended Questions relating to Multiple Sexual Partners (MSP) being turned into Subthemes

Multiple Sexual Partners:

CODES	SUBTHEME
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Gaining thrill from having sex with multiple people is enjoyable ● Having sex with multiple people is seen as moderately fun ● Having multiple sexual partners is a personal fun choice ● Having multiple sexual partners allows more freedom ● Having multiple sexual partners is personally convenient and fun ● Having multiple sexual partners can be experimented with at a young age and is fun ● Having sex with other people can be seen as a new experience ● Prefers to explore their fun interests at a young age ● Sleeping with other people helps to overcome break-ups 	Enjoyment and Thrill-Seeking
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Enjoying the emotional connection from sex with partners ● Having multiple sexual partners improves self-esteem ● Having multiple sexual partners provides attention to the person ● Facing a break from romance changes perspectives on sexual partnerships ● Having sex with new people helps overcome break-ups ● Break-up naturally led to having sex with other people ● Bad experience with romantic relationships led to not seeking romantic relationships again ● Seeking multiple sexual partners with similar interests 	Emotional and Psychological Factors
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Do not enjoy the commitment to one person ● Moving on from person to person for sexual interest ● Adapting to environments as people do not enjoy settling for one person ● Not interested in a romantic relationship ● Having multiple sexual partners reduces the issue of commitment responsibility ● Scheduling is not flexible in romantic relationships ● Short time frames at university make romantic relationships pointless 	Avoidance of Commitment and Monogamy
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Having multiple sexual partners increases chances of finding sexual fulfilment ● Difficult to find a person who fulfils sexual pleasure and enjoyment ● Having multiple sexual partners can help find the right person for you ● Having multiple sexual partners allows you to find the person who you can settle with romantically 	Searching for Sexual and Romantic Fulfilment
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Social media creating concepts for situationships ● Having multiple sexual partners is influenced by breaking gendered norms ● Viewing the concept of multiple sexual partners as a mix of positives and negatives ● Past personal experiences impacted views on relationship concepts 	Influence of Social Norms and Media
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Having multiple sexual partners is a matter of personal preference ● Having multiple sexual partners is not a problem as long as it is enjoyable ● Having multiple sexual partners is circumstantial as long as it is enjoyable ● Wishing for a personal choice to experience sexual preferences with other people ● Decision to have sex with multiple people was not conscious ● No influence to seek new sexual partners; it happened in the moment 	Personal Autonomy and Circumstantial Choices

<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Feeling comfortable to have sex with multiple people	
<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Lack of structure in routines impacts mood negatively● Having sex with the same person can be boring and lacks excitement● Having multiple sexual partners is an issue if within different time periods● Enjoying the control of changing the people to have sex with	Structure and Lifestyle Factors

Appendix X: Subthemes from Open-ended Questions relating to Multiple Sexual Partners (MSP) being turned into Themes

SUBTHEMES	FINAL THEME
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Enjoyment and Thrill-Seeking ● Emotional and Psychological Factors 	Pleasure and Self-gratification
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Avoidance of Commitment and Monogamy ● Searching for Sexual and Romantic Fulfilment 	Relationship Attitudes and Avoidance of Commitment
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Personal Autonomy and Circumstantial Choices ● Structure and Lifestyle Factors 	Personal and Lifestyle Factors
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Influence of Social Norms and Media 	Social and Cultural Influence

Appendix Y: Quotes from Open-ended Questions relating to Sending Explicit Sexual Images (ESI) being turned into Codes

Explicit Sexual Images (ESI):

Quotes	Codes
<p>when I feel like I want to be closer to them</p>	<p>Sending photos provides closeness in a relationship</p>
<p>Me and my boyfriend are long distance, so sometimes we become sexually aroused</p>	<p>Allows to fulfill sexual desire when in a long-distance relationship</p>
<p>and it just happens.</p>	<p>Heat of the moment results in sending explicit sexual images</p>
<p>when they ask for it and i don't want to disappoint or seem boring</p>	<p>Peer pressured to send images to avoid being seen negatively</p>
<p>i think it is because it;s considered normal to see if you will put your time and effort into that person</p>	<p>Sending images is seen as normal to show effort in a person</p>
<p>I've been with my boyfriend for a long time but we are long-distance since university I am in a long-distance relationship and we send each other pictures and videos because it helps us feel closer and more connected even when we aren't together.</p>	<p>Sending images allows to stay connected during long-distance relationships</p> <p>Sending images improves closeness in a relationship</p>

<p>How I'm feeling in the moment and how strong my feelings are</p>	<p>Sending images is impacted by a person's mood and sexual drive</p>
<p>trust are for the person I'm sending it to</p>	<p>Trust plays a role in sending sexual explicit images</p>
<p>I get motivated by people who may appreciate it back and may be interested in sharing these images</p>	<p>Only sending images based on whether the other person would do the same</p>
<p>My partner is long distance so it helps to maintain the relationship</p>	<p>Sending images maintains the stability of long-distance relationships</p>
<p>feeling good about the way I look and the compliments that come with the photo</p>	<p>Sending images provides compliments and improves self-image</p>
<p>My boyfriend and I are long-distance as he does not attend university, so I don't get to see him often.</p>	<p>Sending images provides a way to stay connected with a long-distance relationship</p>
<p>I think it's quite important, and quite romantic too, for us to connect sexually without having to be with each other physically.</p>	<p>Sending images is important in gaining sexual connection and fulfillment</p>
<p>It makes you feel good about yourself especially when you get compliments</p>	<p>Sending images makes a person feel good about themselves and provides compliments</p>
<p>Mutual desire between me and</p>	<p>Sending images is a mutual agreement</p>

<p>my partner.</p> <p>I have never felt pressured by him to do so but I have enjoyed doing it</p> <p>of my own accord in a 'teasing' manner</p> <p>or to engage in sexual activities as best as we can being in a long-distance relationship.</p> <p>Knowing i can trust them,</p> <p>because its fun and we both feel closer to each other,</p> <p>because we encourage each other to</p> <p>I am motivated by other people wanting to send sexual images for example Maybe the intimacy you get with your partner and it's important not being able to see someone regularly and if you are in a relationship</p> <p>To please my long term partner as I know how much he likes them</p> <p>Just spices up our relationship a bit, and allows us to build and strengthen our relationship.</p> <p>Plus, it's always fun to send and</p>	<p>between both parties</p> <p>Lack of peer pressure to send images but does provide joy</p> <p>Sending images is a form of sexual teasing towards the other person</p> <p>Sending images maximises sexual intimacy and drive whilst in a long-distance relationship</p> <p>Sending images is comfortable due to trust</p> <p>Sending images is both fun and provides closer to connection with partner</p> <p>Sending sexual images is encouraged by both parties</p> <p>Sending sexual images due to motivation from peers</p> <p>Intimacy increases between partners when sending images</p> <p>Sending images seen as a way to engage with partner whilst long-distance</p> <p>Sending images to sexually please another person</p> <p>Sending images improve general sexual intimacy</p> <p>Sending images strengthens relationships</p> <p>Sending images seen as fun to send between your partner</p>
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<p>receive when it's your partner.</p> <p>for when i am not with my partner, it also looks good</p> <p>I like the praise and approval from others</p> <p>which makes me feel better about myself</p> <p>It doesn't appeal to me and my boyfriend that much but it can be arousing for both of us if we haven't seen each other in a while</p> <p>The desire to feel sexy and to let my partner know how I'm feeling, also for them to gain sexual pleasure from it</p> <p>my boyfriend only no one else as I know he wouldn't show anyone I decide to only send them to my partner as I am obviously loyal to him. The thought of sending explicit content does not excite me in the slightest.</p> <p>i only share with my boyfriend because i know i can trust him we've been together for almost</p>	<p>Sending images makes the person look good</p> <p>Sending images provides positive praise and approval from others</p> <p>Sending images makes the person sending them feel better about themselves</p> <p>Sending images provides sexual arousal if partners have not engaged with each other for a while</p> <p>The desire to feel sexy influences sending images Sending images is a way to express how a person is feeling</p> <p>Sending images is strictly between two people only</p> <p>Sending images is strictly between two people only</p> <p>Sending images between partners only to show loyalty</p> <p>Only sending images to a partner you have trusted for years</p>
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<p>4 years</p> <p>the way they talk and how they come across online. But obviously, after you have had multiple conversations and are comfortable when the conversation leads to that</p> <p>With my long-term boyfriend since we have become long-distance a few months ago I only share with the person I am in a committed, exclusive relationship with because I can trust they won't share it with other people or use it against me in any way.</p> <p>My relationship with the person, the trust I have and how much I like them Factors include people I regard as close friends/people I trust and know I would only share this content with my partner, however if I was single I would only send content to those I could trust and had met multiple times before my boyfriend is the only person i would send and receive photos from As I've mentioned, I'm in a relationship so he is the only person I would send explicit content of myself to.</p>	<p>Having multiple conversations leads to sending sexual images</p> <p>Only sending images to the person you are in a committed relationship with</p> <p>Trusting sexual images will not be shared to other people</p> <p>Sending images based on the relationship, trust and liking for the person</p> <p>Sending images to those they deem close partners or in a relationship</p> <p>Only sending images to those they trust and met multiple times</p> <p>Only sending images to their partner in a relationship</p>
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<p>It had to be someone that I knew pretty well so I felt safe. Definitely how close I am with that person and how trustworthy they are.</p> <p>I have never and will never do so with a casual partner as that trust hasn't been built or earned, but given time and commitment I have been willing to do it with people I was in relationships with.</p> <p>If the person seems trustworthy, for example by putting themselves forward first and then making me feel safe in doing so myself. If the person seems to genuinely care about me, we have a good back and forth flow in communication and things feel natural, just because its fun to, etc. Personally I need somewhat of an emotional connection but the main aspect is about trust. Trusting them knowing they wont share it round, put me in a bad light, use me for their own personal reasons, and that sort of flow of events.</p> <p>I decide by people who may be interested in me wanting to share and factors which</p>	<p>Sending images to those who make them feel safe and are trustworthy</p> <p>Only sending images to those whos trust has been built or earned</p> <p>Sending images to those who are seen as trustworthy</p> <p>Sending images to those make them feel safe sending them</p> <p>Only sending images to those who show care and interest in the person</p> <p>Sending images primarily because it is fun</p> <p>Prior trust and connection needed before sending sexual images</p> <p>Only sending images to those they trust won't use it against them</p> <p>Sharing images only to those who show interest in the person</p> <p>Deciding to share images based on closeness with the person</p>
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determine this is by how close I am with these people

I personally only share those types of content with my partner someone you are in a relationship with as you trust them I only share it with my partner, influenced by my current mood I will only ever send it to my long term partner. I will never send anything to someone I do not know, or I am not in a long term relationship with.

if i trust them and know [them] in real life

Depending on the energy given by the person i am talking to then i will be more influenced to do such

My boyfriend and only my boyfriend because we are in a committed relationship and not interested in anyone else

People who I am having a sexual relationship with .

yes. I enjoyed it, its better with

Sending images to only their partner in a relationship due to built trust

Current mood impacts if images are sent to a partner

Only sending images to those they trust and know in real life

Influenced to send images based on the person's character

Only sending images to their partner and not interested to send to other people

Sending images to those with a sexual relationship

Joy is gained from sending images but trust increases the joy more

<p>someone you trust</p> <p>Yes, as i believe there is little risk as i trust that my partner will not share them. We also both gain pleasure from it.</p> <p>yes but only to one person and not very often</p> <p>Yes because i have been doing it for a long time</p> <p>Yes because it's consensual and I know they won't be shared around yes but only to someone I am in a committed and exclusive relationship with and who I can trust.</p> <p>Yes as it supports the relationship between myself and my partner when I cannot see them in person</p> <p>yes as i enjoy the exciting feeling of sending explicit photos to my partner and</p>	<p>Trusted that partner will not send the images to others</p> <p>Sexual pleasure is gained from sending images from both parties</p> <p>Only sending the images rarely to one person</p> <p>Feeling comfortable to send images as it has been done for a long time</p> <p>Sending images only if its consensual and not sent to others</p> <p>Only sending images to those in an exclusive romantic relationship</p> <p>Only sending images to those who's trust has been built or earned</p> <p>Sending images provides support when parties are not physically present</p> <p>Sending images provides excitement and receiving them from others provides pleasure</p> <p>Sending images allows the maintenance of a sexual romantic relationship</p>
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<p>receiving them</p> <p>Yes because it's a great way for me and my boyfriend to still feel a romantic sexual connection to each other.</p> <p>Yes and with my boyfriend, due to us being in a long-distance relationship and my willingness to do so I can see it happening again.</p> <p>yes if it meant i or my future wouldn't be put at risk. I don't have problems sending if I have the sense they won't spread them round maliciously</p> <p>No-However it depends if other want to continue to share in sending these types of images</p> <p>Yes probably as mentioned it is a form of intimacy you have yes with someone I am in a relationship with but no one else Yes-it makes my partner happy and I like pleasing him</p> <p>Yes - only to my partner as I trust him and know it is for his eyes only.</p> <p>yes because i think it looks nice and me and my partner both</p>	<p>Only sending images to those in a long-term relationship</p> <p>Willing to send images in hopes the behaviour occurs again</p> <p>Only sending images if the person's future is not damaged</p> <p>Feeling comfortable to send images as long as it is not against them maliciously</p> <p>Sending images depends on if the other party wants to send the images back</p> <p>Sending images is seen as a form of intimacy</p> <p>Only sending the images to someone they are in a relationship with</p> <p>Sending images to make their partner happy</p> <p>Sending images to gain pleasure from seeing their partner enjoy the images</p> <p>Sending images based on trust with partner and for them only</p> <p>Sending images makes the person look nice and provides enjoyment</p> <p>Sending images depends on the person's personal preferences</p> <p>Only sending images if the person will not</p>
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<p>enjoy it Yes however, it depends on the person i am sending it to Yes if I knew I wasn't going to see my boyfriend for some time Yes, because my partner likes them and finds them sexy</p>	<p>see their partner for some time</p> <p>Enjoys sending the images because they feel sexy and their partner enjoys them</p>
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Appendix Z: Codes from Open-ended Questions relating to Sending Explicit Sexual Images (ESI) being turned into Subthemes

Explicit Sexual Images:

CODES	SUBTHEME
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Sending images provides closeness in a relationship ● Sending images improves closeness in a relationship ● Sending images strengthens relationships ● Sending images is both fun and provides a closer connection with a partner ● Sending images is important in gaining sexual connection and fulfilment ● Sending images provides a way to stay connected in long-distance relationships ● Sending images maintains the stability of long-distance relationships ● Sending images allows the maintenance of a sexual romantic relationship ● Sending images maximises sexual intimacy and drive whilst in a long-distance relationship ● Sending images is seen as a way to engage with a partner whilst long-distance ● Sending images allows fulfilling sexual desire when in a long-distance relationship 	<p>Relationship Maintenance and Closeness</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Trust plays a role in sending sexually explicit images ● Only sending images based on whether the other person would do the same ● Sending images is comfortable due to trust ● Only sending images to those they trust and have met multiple times ● Only sending images to a partner they have trusted for years ● Trusting that sexual images will not be shared with other people ● Sending images based on the relationship, trust, and liking for the person ● Only sending images to those whose trust has been built or earned ● Only sending images to those who show care and interest in the person ● Prior trust and connection needed before sending sexual images ● Trusted that partner will not send the images elsewhere ● Only sending images to those they trust will not use them against them maliciously 	<p>Trust and Safety as Key Factors</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Sending images provides excitement, and receiving them from others provides pleasure ● Sending images is a form of sexual teasing the other person ● Sexual pleasure is gained from sending images for both parties ● Sending images to sexually please another partner ● Sending images improves general sexual intimacy ● Sending images provides sexual arousal if partners have not engaged with each other for a while ● Sending images is seen as a form of intimacy ● Sending images is a way to provide sexual pleasure 	<p>Sexual Pleasure and Excitement</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Sending images makes a person feel good about themselves and provides compliments ● Sending images provides compliments and improves self-image ● Sending images makes the person look nice and provides enjoyment ● Sending images provides positive praise and approval from others ● The desire to feel sexy influences sending images 	<p>Self-Image and Validation</p>

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enjoys sending images because they feel sexy and their partner enjoys them 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sending sexual images is encouraged by both parties • Peer pressured to send images to avoid being seen negatively • Sending images due to motivation from peers • Lack of peer pressure to send images but does provide joy 	Social and Peer Influence
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Heat of the moment results in sending explicit sexual images • Current mood impacts whether images are sent to a partner • Sending images is impacted by a person's mood and sexual drive • Having multiple conversations leads to sending sexual images • Only sending images if the person will not see their partner for some time 	Situational and Impulsive Decisions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sending images is strictly between two people only • Only sending images if it is consensual and not shared with others • Only sending images to those in an exclusive romantic relationship • Sending images depends on if the other party wants to send them back • Only sending images if the person's future is not damaged • Only sending images to those in a long-term relationship 	Consent and Ethical Considerations

Appendix AA: Subthemes from Open-ended Questions relating to Sending Explicit Sexual Images (ESI) being turned into Themes

SUBTHEMES	FINAL THEME
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Relationship Maintenance and Closeness ● Trust and Safety as Key Factors 	<p style="text-align: center;">Relationship and Emotional Motivations</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Sexual Pleasure and Excitement ● Self-Image and Validation 	<p style="text-align: center;">Sexual and Psychological Gratification</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Situational and Impulsive Decisions ● Consent and Ethical Considerations 	<p style="text-align: center;">Situational and Ethical Considerations</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Social and Peer Influence 	<p style="text-align: center;">External and Social Pressures</p>

Appendix AB: Distribution plots showcasing positive skew of data spread for Risky Sexual Behaviours

Distribution Plots

US_Summary

MSP_Summary

Appendix AC: Distribution plots showcasing bell-shaped curve of data spread for Dark Triad Personality Traits

Machiavellianism_Score

Narcissism_Score

